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CASTIEL 2

**Coordination & Support
for National Competence Centres on a European Level Phase 2**

Project Number: 101102047

D4.1

**Initial Report on the Actions performed to support the
NCCs and the CoEs' Interactions with Industry**

EuroHPC
 Joint Undertaking

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List of abbreviations

AAT	Automated Assessment Tool
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interfaces
BoF	Bird Of Feather
CASTIEL[1-2]	Phase [1 or 2] of CASTIEL
C2ISS	EuroCC-CASTIEL Information Sharing System
CC	Competence Centre
CoE	Centre of Excellence
COLA	Collaboration Agreement
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
EC	European Commission
EDIH	European Digital Innovation Hub
EUROCC[1-2]	Phase [1 or 2] of EUROCC
GA	Grant Agreement
HPC	High Performance Computing
HPC+	HPC/HPDA/AI
HPDA	High Performance Data Analytics
IWG	Industry Working Group
JU	Joint Undertaking
M	Months
NCC	National Competence Centre
PMT	Project Management Team
PO	Project Officer
SME	Small and Medium-Sized Enterprise
TPR	Technical Progress Report
T.X	Task X
Q	Quarter
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

CASTIEL2 is the Coordination and Support Action (CSA) of the EUROCC2 project composed of 33 National Competence Centres (NCCs) and of the active 10 Centres of Excellences (CoEs) in Europe. The Work Package 4 (WP4) of CASTIEL2 is titled “NCCs, CoEs and Industry Interactions”. The overall objective of this work package is to establish and support effective interactions between the NCCs, the CoEs and European industry to support adoption and use of HPC (and associated technologies like AI and HPDA) in the private (particularly SMEs) sectors considering the specific needs of the national & European HPC ecosystem.

This is being performed by CASTIEL2-WP4 by working on three main axes:

- On the topics related to the structuration of services and the promotion of those services, particularly (but not only limited to that) through the topic of the LinkHPC platform (previously called “Marketplace”)
- On the support to the NCCs and CoEs to increase and extend engagements with established and potential industrial end-users (in particular SMEs), and to amplify the NCCs and the CoEs’ collective impact through actions like the “Code of the month” series, through coordination to attend collaboratively sectorial events or organisation of thematic webinars.
- On ensuring the communications between the representatives of the NCCs and CoEs working on industry topics, to provide a clear exchange of knowledge, lessons learned and best practices regarding industry topics inside and outside the EUROCC2-CASTIEL2 networks

This deliverable D4.1 is the first report on the actions performed to support the NCCs and the CoEs’ interactions with industry by CASTIEL2-WP4 during the first year of CASTIEL2. This document presents the strategies, the methodologies but also the main outcomes and results of the works done with regards to the industry interactions topics among the NCCs and the CoEs thanks to the coordination and support from CASTIEL2 during the first year of the project, and what this brought to the NCCs and CoEs as new skills, tools or instruments for their benefits, to support them in their interactions with industry as a whole.

This deliverable reports and presents key actions and outcomes that occurred during 2023. Therefore, the work performed in a dedicated task force about the LinkHPC platform (previously called “marketplace”) is explained, along with, more generally, the actions done to support NCCs and CoEs when it comes to services available for industry: e.g. the “business” training of the NCCs or the collection of summarised information for the benefit of the NCCs and of the CoEs about how to structure their services for industry or how to interact with industry about their services. There are also descriptions of the setup of the “Code of the month” series, the organisation of the recurring “Industry virtual coffee breaks” and the organisations of several webinars with other initiatives to inform the NCCs and CoEs (e.g. the FF4EuroHPC webinar about the results of the experiments with SMEs, the ETP4HPC webinar about their market study, the GAIA-X webinar, etc.). Finally, explanations about the setup and monitoring of several task forces like the “SMEs assessment tool” task force led by NCC Slovenia and the “EuroCC Supercomputer Accelerator” task force led by NCC Austria are also included in this deliverable.

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1 Introduction

CASTIEL2 is the Coordination and Support Action (CSA) of the EUROCC2 project composed of 33 National Competence Centres (NCCs) and of the active 10 Centres of Excellences (CoEs) in Europe. In order to identify and close the gaps due to the diverse levels of maturity between the different nations, and to make them interact with the existing CoEs, CASTIEL2 is bringing together a core consortium to setup a framework of activities that support the evolution of all NCCs and CoEs and facilitate their sharing of knowledge and expertise.

The Work Package 4 (WP4) of CASTIEL2 “NCCs, CoEs and Industry Interactions” has for overall objective to establish and support effective interactions between the NCCs, the CoEs and European industry to support adoption and use of HPC (and associated technologies like AI and HPDA) in the private (particularly SMEs) sectors considering the specific needs of the national & European HPC ecosystem. This is being performed by CASTIEL2-WP4 by working on three main axes:

- On the topics related to the structuration of the services and the promotion of those services, particularly (but not only limited to that) through the topic of the LinkHPC platform (previously called “Marketplace”)
- On the support to the NCCs and CoEs to increase and extend engagements with established and potential industrial end-users (in particular SMEs), and to amplify the NCCs and the CoEs’ collective impact through actions like “Code of the month” series, coordination to attend collaboratively sectorial events, organisation of thematic webinars, etc.
- On ensuring the communications between the representatives of the NCCs and CoEs working on industry topics, to provide a clear exchange of knowledge, lessons learned and best practices regarding industry topics inside and outside the EuroCC2-CASTIEL2 networks

This deliverable D4.1 presents the strategies, the methodologies but also the main outcomes, the results of the works done and their added value for the NCCs and CoEs, when it comes to industry interactions topics among the NCCs and the CoEs thanks to the coordination and support from CASTIEL2 during the first year of the project.

Section 2 of this deliverable presents in more details the overall objective of CASTIEL2-WP4, its management and the way this WP interacts with the NCCs and the CoEs.

Section 3 explains the objectives, the strategy, the performed work, the outcomes from the year 2023, and the plans for the next steps of the Task 4.1 “Contribution to the C2ISS and the evolved EuroCC ACCESS Portal Design (including the marketplace)”.

Section 4 explains the objectives, the strategy, the performed work, the outcomes from the year 2023, and the plans for the next steps of the Task 4.2 “NCCs, CoEs – industry interaction support”.

Section 5 explains the objectives, the strategy, the performed work, the outcomes from the year 2023, and the plans for the next steps of the Task 4.3 “NCCs – CoEs Exchange and Knowledge - Sharing on Industry Interactions”.

Section 6 presents the topics that are transversally monitored by WP4.

Section 7 summarises the key major achievements and provides concluding remarks.

Section 8 and 9 gather respectively the list of references and the annexes.

2 Work Package 4 of CASTIEL2: “NCCs, CoEs and Industry Interactions”

2.1 Objectives and Management of Work Package 4

Work Package 4 (WP4) of CASTIEL2 aims at establishing and supporting effective interactions between the NCCs, the CoEs and European industry to support adoption and use of HPC (and associated technologies like AI and HPDA) in the private (particularly SMEs) sectors considering the specific needs of the national & European HPC ecosystem. To achieve this main objective, WP4 initiates and organizes actions to understand the challenges and the requirements of the interactions of the NCCs and the CoEs with industry in order to find ways, together with the NCCs and CoEs, to address these.

CASTIEL2-WP4 is structured and working along three main tasks; its structure and the working mode are summarised in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Structure and working mode of CASTIEL2-WP4

Following the Grant Agreement (GA), Task 4.1 (T4.1) is in charge of the « Contribution to the C2ISS and the evolved EuroCC ACCESS Portal Design (including the marketplace)”. For practical reasons, as the “marketplace” will not have a commerce aspect, and to highlight the *ecosystem interaction and connection* aspect, the “marketplace” was re-named “LinkHPC platform”. Therefore, T4.1 is in charge of the discussions about the LinkHPC platform.

Additionally, as this concept of marketplace/LinkHPC platform is actually about services and offers and about how to practically support the NCCs and CoEs to develop them, T4.1 also undertook during the year 2023 several actions and initiatives in favour of the development and enrichment of offers and services, and the promotion of those among the NCCs and the CoEs.

Task 4.2 (T4.2) is in charge of “NCCs, CoEs – Industry Interaction Support”. T4.2 supports the CoEs and the NCCs to increase and extend engagements with established and potential industrial end-users (in particular SMEs), and to amplify the NCCs and the CoEs’ collective impact.

Task 4.3 (T4.3) is in charge of “NCCs – CoEs Exchange and Knowledge - Sharing on Industry Interactions”. It manages an “industry relations” working group with NCCs and CoEs as members, which discusses and frames the challenges and requirements of establishing effective

and impactful interaction with industry, by for instance ensuring that both NCCs and CoEs have access to all relevant industrial interaction information and existing solutions.

Remark about the interactions with the CoEs: many activities of WP4 involve NCCs, CoEs and often other players of the (European and world wide) HPC Ecosystem. CASTIEL2 has very close and special relationships to the 10 JU-funded HPC CoEs who started in January 2023 along with CASTIEL2 and that are currently signing a collaboration agreement with CASTIEL2.

These 10 CoEs are part of the CASTIEL2 industry working group managed by WP4 and part of the inner “NCC & CoE network”. In addition to those 10, the older 6 already running, EC-funded CoEs (which will end between end 2023 and mid 2024: TREX, NOMAD-2, PerMedCoE, CoEC, RAISE, CompBioMed) were nonetheless considered also as relevant and interesting stakeholders of the HPC ecosystem, in view of their objectives that are close to those of the newly launched CoEs and in view of their many ongoing collaborations with NCCs stemming from the previous phase of CASTIEL1. Thus, WP4 has strived to involve these 6 CoE wherever this was possible even without some more formalised relationship, which is currently being established with the 10 new CoEs.

In particular, this concerned the activities of the NCC-CoE workshop in April 2023 (organised by CASTIEL2-WP2 and during which CASTIEL2-WP4 organized the specific session about the industry topics, see Table 7) and the “Code of the Month” series of webinars (see section 4).

At end of 2023, the PMT of EuroCC2 produced a questionnaire to collect information about collaboration and impact from the NCCs within the EuroCC2 project. This questionnaire included questions about industry topics (challenges, strategies and perspectives) and the LinkHPC platform. The results being processed and presented during December 2023 by EuroCC2-PMT in a specific deliverable D1.6 for EuroCC2, CASTIEL2-WP4 will use, during the next year, the outcomes presented in this deliverable D1.6 that concern industry in order to plan specific relevant actions to provide to the NCCs the skills or tools or methods to address their specific challenges.

3 Task 4.1 “Contribution to the C2ISS and the Evolved EuroCC ACCESS Portal Design (Including the Marketplace)”

3.1 Objectives and Strategy Implementation for Task 4.1

Task 4.1 is in charge of collecting the specific requirements, both from the NCCs and the CoEs, relevant and adapted to their actual and potential industrial end-users on the expectations and requirements for the evolved EuroCC Access portal (including the marketplace/LinkHPC Platform). The initial plan was to gather information from the NCCs and CoEs during the first year in order to be able to have a prototype by end of year 1 and to have the marketplace/LinkHPC Platform prototype s’ first runs during year 2.

The topic “LinkHPC platform” was progressing at a relative slow rate for the first six months of EUROCC2-CASTIEL2 due to the following reasons: firstly, due to the complexity of this topic “LinkHPC platform” (e.g. how to design a common template for so different NCCs? And there are questions and issues with regards to the national constraints and various politics on this topic), and secondly to the absence of the official review report from the JU after the end of EUROCC1-CASTIEL1. Indeed, questions were asked to the reviewers and the JU by the industry working group about this topic and the related orientations to consider about it, and not knowing the answers obliged CASTIEL2 to proceed with carefully chosen actions in the meantime. However, the progress of the timeline got back on track in June 2023. The outcomes of the work done on this topic are presented in section 3.2

Therefore, in the meantime, in order to still provide relevant support and coordination to the NCCs and CoEs on the broad topic “services and offers and about how to support the NCCs and CoEs to develop them”, T4.1 undertook in parallel many actions and initiatives in favour of the development and enrichment of offers and services and the promotion of those among the NCCs and CoEs. The outcomes of the work done on these other key topics regarding services and development of the interactions with industry are presented in section 3.3.

3.2 “LinkHPC platform”: Actions Undertaken During Year 1 and Results

With/For the NCCs

(1) Initial questionnaire to collect interests for various features for the future central hub

In June 2023, CASTIEL2-WP5 created and launched a questionnaire to collect the feedbacks from the NCCs and the CoEs about the important or necessary features for the future design of the C2ISS (EuroCC-CASTIEL Information Sharing System). CASTIEL-2-WP4 collaborated to the creation of this questionnaire by providing the questions about a potential future central hub of the marketplace/LinkHPC Platform. Indeed, the current idea would be to have a future central hub “EU LinkHPC platform” that would aggregate selected information from the national “LinkHPC platforms” to display them centrally at the EU level. And this central hub “EU LinkHPC platform” would be articulated with the C2ISS as presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Global concept of the “LinkHPC platform“ (formerly called “marketplace”) & articulation with C2ISS

By July 06th 2023, 5 CoEs and 19 NCCs provided feedbacks. To ensure a better representativity for the 10 CoEs, CASTIEL2-WP2 and WP4 decided to re-open the parts about the competences and the future central hub of the marketplace/LinkHPC Platform during October 2023 and they reminded the CoEs to answer the questionnaire. The detailed complete answers are summarised and presented in Annex 1.

The collected complete answers show that except for the codes, almost all the NCCs are generally interested in displaying and seeing every available information when it comes to services, the ecosystem, the events and the other areas to all kind of users (industry, public administration, research centres, etc). The CoEs have a little more specific interests, for instance particularly on the codes and their related services, on training, consultancy and the external ecosystem. To concretely assess the priorities and to better design the exact structure to present all these elements of information on the future hub of the Marketplace/LinkHPC platform, it was decided to use an existing solution (namely the French “CC-FR marketplace”) to be able for the interested NCCs to test and provide in-depth needed improvements for a future common template through a dedicated task force “Test of LinkHPC platform/marketplace to design a services structure”.

- (2) Task force about the “LinkHPC platform”, organised with NCC France: “Test of LinkHPC platform to design a services structure”

Outcomes and follow-up at the end of phase 1: At the end of the phase 1 of EuroCC /CASTIEL, the results of the benchmark done during phase 1 about the potential solutions for

a “marketplace” were presented during the review in March 2023. The related questions asking for the JU orientations and recommendations (about a set-up of a potential European unique marketplace) were presented to the JU and the reviewers. There were limited received elements of answers during the review itself (a priori, the solution presented by NCC France was positively received during the review, and the reviewers highlighted the importance of having some homogeneity in the EuroCC network while working on this topic). The actual written report was received by CASTIEL2 only on November 29th 2023, allowing for very little time to take into account the provided feedbacks by end of year 1 of this phase 2 (December 31st 2023).

Update of the working name/terminology: As the planned structure will not have a commerce aspect, and to better highlight the *linking the ecosystem* aspect, it was decided from April 2023 to stop using the word “Marketplace” and to replace it by “LinkHPC platform”

CASTIEL2-WP4 proposal to collaboratively design a common structure for the national LinkHPC platform: in agreement with the PMT, as by June 2023, there was no written clear feedbacks after the review of phase 1 about the plans and actual expectations of the JU regarding the topic “marketplace”, it was decided to at least proceed with launching a task force to work on a common template/structure for a “marketplace”. This way, there were actual progresses on a specific part of this topic, as it was decided to focus on developing first a template (i.e. an architecture skeleton) appropriate and validated by the interested NCCs, that could be deployed by all interested NCC in their country in 2024.

This template or structure would be the unique common reference for all NCCs, the plan being to have it ready by end of 2023; in order to allow the NCCs to work, in a second step, on actual national implementations during 2024 while CASTIEL2 would work on developing a central hub to gather at a unique European level the selected national data. The “national implementation” part would have to be discussed first with the PMT and the JU to see what would be the flexibility for the NCCs in terms of providers, solutions and compatibility with the central hub. For the task force to not start from scratch and to have a common object to work with, CASTIEL2-WP4 discussed with NCC France to allow some access to the structure of their CC-FR platform (through a specially developed English test version of it) and to co-organise with them the management of the task force working on the design of a future common unique structure for all NCCs.

This proposal, established by CASTIEL2-WP4 after discussions with PMT team was shared with the industry working group and agreed upon on June 29th 2023. During Summer 2023, the procurement was launched to NCC France for them to prepare, using their “CC-FR Marketplace”, the English updated version or prototype of a test version for the national LinkHPC platform.

The task force, gathering 15 NCCs (list in Annex 2) was launched on September 7th 2023, with the presentation of the plan and timeline (summarised in Figure 3) for this task force. The plan being to be able to share with all NCCs by beginning of 2024 a consistent unique structure, to be used by all potential future NCCs national platforms. The unicity of the template or structure is a key element in being able to build a common central hub in the future, articulated with the C2ISS to automatically display at a unique place the information about services and industry ecosystems available in the 33 NCCs.

Figure 3: Initial timeline of the task force "Test of LinkHPC platform to design a services structure"

As indicated on the timeline, on October 16th 2023, the EN version being online, a tutorial was done in live online to the task force members, in order for NCC France to show them how to test the platform and how to provide their feedbacks about it through a common form (extract in Annex 2). A follow-up meeting was held on November 6th 2023 to collect the very first feedbacks or questions of the task force members regarding their tests of the EN platform. A "consolidation-summary" first meeting took on November 29th for CASTIEL2-WP4 and NCC France to present the consolidated common feedback from the task force, and discuss any debatable topic with all the task force member. Given the number of items to be discussed and agreed together for updates in the test version, a second meeting is planned for December 11th 2023. The outcome of these actions and of the consolidation meeting will be the core of the report planned for early 2024 to provide the proposed common architecture of such a platform. Following the updates to be implemented on the test version (thanks to the work of the task force), users tests could be planned beginning of 2024 with SMEs contacts of the NCCs to check the user-"friendliness" of the interface and the relevance of this future common structure.

With/For the CoEs

- (3) Initial questionnaire to collect interests for various features for the future central hub of the LinkHPC platform

The same questionnaire was sent to the CoEs as the one for the NCCs. The outcomes of this questionnaire are presented in the previous paragraph.

With/For the NCCs (1) Initial questionnaire and detailed in Annex 1.

- (4) Meetings to discuss links of the services portals of the CoEs with the LinkHPC platform & the C2SSI, co-organised with WP2 and WP5

Some of the older CoEs have already some services portal on their own, and some recent ones are planning to have one. To more precisely define what are their services portals, how to link them with the future central hub of the LinkHPC platform or the C2SSI, CASTIEL2-WP4 co-organised with WP2 and WP5 meetings with the CoEs. The collected information during this

meeting and during the follow-up interactions with the industry champions of the CoEs is summarised in the Annex 3.

In a nutshell, the outcomes of these discussions and interactions were that for all CoEs except EXCELLERAT P2, the “services portals” are actually usually webpages listing their available services (in the form of a list or a basic catalogue) and a mere contact form. Therefore, except for EXCELLERAT P2 (and their services portal: <https://services.excellerat.eu/> currently being re-designed), it should not be complicated to ensure links and visibility of these webpages and their related information through either the future central hub of the LinkHPC platform or the C2SSI.

The case of EXCELLERAT P2 is different as this CoE has created a real portal, <https://services.excellerat.eu/>, to display their services during their phase 1 and during their phase 2 (started in January 2023), they plan to update and improve it. Therefore, a dedicated meeting was organised between EXCELLERAT P2, CASTIEL2-WP4 and WP5 on October 5th 2023 to discuss how to liaise between these projects and to ensure links between the future solutions and platforms. Interactions will be ongoing with EXCELLERAT P2 during the next months to ensure that articulation between their services portal and the future C2SSI and the future central hub of the LinkHPC Platform or the C2SSI will be possible.

Interaction with WP5 about the articulation with the C2SSI, and to coordinate surveys & actions on this topic

To ensure the articulation of the future central hub of the LinkHPC platform with the C2SSI, continuous discussions were ongoing during 2023 with the WP5 of CASTIEL2. This regular interaction took place to ensure that WP5 could design a structure compatible and communicating with a future central hub of the LinkHPC platform, particularly through future APIs.

3.3 Other Key Topics to Support the NCCs & CoEs Services Development: Actions Undertaken During Year 1 and Results

Interests, challenges and needs to interact with industry

(1) of the NCCs

Following the meeting in Stuttgart in January 2023 (details about this meeting in Table 7), several elements were highlighted as key topics for the NCCs for this phase 2 of the projects. They are listed, along with the actions that CASTIEL2-WP4 undertook towards them in the following Table 1, in order to ensure that the activity of WP4 during the project has a positive beneficial impact for the NCCs, by providing relevant support, skills, tools, instruments or processes for them to interact more and more easily with industry.

Expressed priority topics:	CASTIEL2-WP4 follow-up actions / answers
<p><u>-marketing/sales & business development</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1. how to "sell" the NCCs support & services ("Prospects to clients, language & arguments to sell & adapt services") / 	<p>CASTIEL2-WP4 interacted with NCC Austria and NCC Sweden during year 1 of EUROCC2 to organize several actions towards the topic “Marketing-sales”.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A webinar was organised with NCC Austria on March 30th 2023 about

<p>to see also with communication champions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Need to make communication champions discuss with industry champions ("how to approach") 	<p>“How to sell High Tech Products and Services” and what we can learn from Tech-Start-ups”</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CASTIEL2-WP4 interacted with NCC Austria to set up an Autumn academy (starting in November 2023, throughout beginning of 2024), and with NCC Sweden to think about a “sales seminar” (currently scheduled for February 2024) in order to train the NCCs about how to "sell" the NCCs support & services.
<p><u>-marketing/sales & business dypmt</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2. sustainability/build business <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - newsletter (structured system) to share info about funding schemes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CASTIEL2-WP4 regularly updates the industry champions about the funding available through the EC or the JU, and shares information from ETP4HPC regarding their webinars organised to inform the ecosystem about funding schemes.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - legal trouble (software license) /contract templates/ memorandum of action or proof of good will 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Regarding the need for legal advice, it was forwarded to the legal task of EUROCC2
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - experts/ consultancy platform /external experts /collaboration between NCCs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Regarding the importance of collaboration and a need for an “experts” or consultancy platform, this is addressed through the Cluster tool and the “EuroCC Supercomputer Accelerator” task force.
<p><u>- questions asked by the industry champions:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1. Central pay per use scheme from JU is needed <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Companies need to know what they sign up for 	<p>CASTIEL2-WP4 investigated about the pay per use scheme in all the JU supercomputers and produced a report¹ about the industry access to the JU infrastructures in order to provide practical information to the NCCs about the topic “Access for Industry to EuroHPC JU Systems”</p>
<p><u>- questions asked by the industry champions:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2. JU should provide a scheme for access to HPC for PoC and training events. At the moment it’s either benchmark/ development access or one to one with the systems which is not ideal. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - (question which would have to be rather asked to the JU,)
<p><u>- questions asked by the industry champions:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3. Interrogation about where do the JU systems fit within the cloud ecosystem (AWS, Azure etc...) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - (question which would have to be rather asked to the JU,)

¹ GUIDE || Access for Industry to EuroHPC JU Systems: <https://www.eurocc-access.eu/services/document-library/>

-Some integration of JU systems is needed.	
<p><u>- questions asked by the industry champions:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4. "external experts" = external to each NCC or external to the whole network? => restrictions of budget concerns which one? 	This question of what is the exact definition of "external experts" in order to invite external experts as speakers to events was forwarded to the PMT for discussing and clarifying that with the JU/PO

Table 1: Priority topics, challenges and questions for the NCCs at end of phase 1 of EuroCC1-CASTIEL1, and the beginning of the phase 2

(2) of the CoEs

Following the online kick-off meeting organised for the CoEs by CASTIEL2-WP2 on April 18 & 19th 2023 (details about the WP4 contribution to this meeting in Table 7), several elements were highlighted as key topics for the CoEs.

They were listed, along with the main information about the CoEs, their interactions with industry and their structure in a detailed report that was produced about these topics and shared only internally with all the NCCs and the CoEs (see [Annex 4, only shared with the JU and the reviewers](#)). Additionally, the following public tables, summarising their goals and structure (Table 2), and summarising the information regarding provision of services by the CoEs (Table 3) were also provided to the NCCs and CoEs for dissemination to their potential prospects about the opportunities offered by the CoEs. This was useful for the NCCs, as it enabled them to potentially display that information on their own websites and to use it to present to their own stakeholders how the EU ecosystem works and what they could potentially use, with which CoE (in terms of expertise, services or codes).

CoE	Complete name/topic	Goal	Structure
EXCELLERAT P2	<i>CoE for supporting supercomputing engineering applications from large scaling to the exascale</i>	<i>To enable the use of simulations workflow at a large scale to exascale computing challenges</i>	7 WPs: -1 PM -3 technical WPs -3 outcome WPs: WP5 centre implementation, WP6 Market context & business development, WP7 Awareness, impact creation & outreach
ChEES2	<i>Centre of Excellence (CoE) in the domain of Solid Earth</i>	<i>Identification of exascale computational challenges in geophysics (natural hazards) in term of capability computing, capacity computing, urgent computing</i>	3 pillars: 1) scientific community 2) EuroHPC infrastructures & NCCs 3) public & private industry parties benefiting from the products & downstream services on geohazards 11 open-source flagships codes 15 simulation cases For the 3rd pillar (public & private parties): co-design with mini-apps with EPI, EUPEX and EuPilot initiative.

			Some TRL 8 or 9, that went into operations.
CEEC	<i>Centre of Excellence in Exascale CFD</i>	<i>Address the extreme-scale computing challenge to enable the use of CFD simulations at exascale.</i>	7 WPs: 3 technical WPs (2, 3, 4) supporting the execution of lighthouse cases WP1, future technologies WP5, dissemination WP6 and PM WP7.
HiDALGO2	<i>Centre of Excellence in Urban-migration simulation topics</i>	<i>bring together advanced solutions (HPC HPDA AI) to provide stakeholders & decision makers tools that would mitigate tragic consequences of climate & civilisation phenomenon by delivering necessary knowledge</i>	The objectives are distributed in Conceptual services: 4 areas: technological, multidisciplinary, socio-scientific, team working objectives. 4 current use cases: urban air project (TRL6), urban buildings (), renewable energy sources, wildfires. Project components (see the slides). Main topics of interest for phase 2: Exascale support for Global Challenges, DATA Exploration and visualisation
MaX3	<i>MAX designs new materials at the exascale</i>	<i>Turn MaX lighthouse codes into exascale-enabled applications Enabling materials for grand challenges</i>	7 WPs: -1 MGT -4 technical WPs -WP5 training & community engagement, WP6 communication, exploitation & dissemination
SPACE	<i>Scalable Parallel Astrophysical Code for Exascale</i> <i>Centre of Excellence (CoE) for HPC astrophysical applications</i>	<i>outstanding quality & volume of data => exceptional challenges to their theoretical interpretation. 8 codes in 3 main themes 5 objectives: to evolve the 8 codes, evolve data analysis & visualisation ecosystem, development of ML techniques, address the energy efficiency issue, federate the A&C community</i>	3 private companies in the consortium WP1: Management WP2/3: science (interaction in WP2 with HW providers) WP4: tools (transversal for the others) WP5: dissemination, outreach, training for the A&C community

<p><u>MultiXScale</u></p>	<p><i>Performance, portability, productivity</i></p>	<p><i>Application co-design for exascale, accelerate development of scientific workflows, interest in co-design</i></p> <p><i>Objective: increase performance, productivity and portability for scientists & pilot multiscale use-cases of societal and industrial significance.</i></p>	<p>2 private companies in the consortium Scientific WPs (2, 3, 4): WP4 includes 3 showcases – one of them is helicopter design with industry partner Leonardo; Technical WPs (1,5); Collaboration with EESSI as a deployment mechanism for software. Large interest from cloud providers.</p> <p>WP7: – Two tasks with specific focus on industry, “Task 7.1 – Scientific applications provisioned on demand” and “Task 7.4 – Industry-oriented training activities”</p>
<p><u>Plasma-PEPSC</u></p>	<p><i>Plasma exascale performance simulations CoE</i></p>	<p><i>Fusion energy research and modern industries depends on plasma science and technology, plasma simulations for societal challenges, HPC, supercomputers and virtual prototyping have an important role in predicting observations and in design => pushing flagship plasma simulation codes to tackle exascale enabled grand challenges.</i></p>	<p>3 technical WPs (2.3.4.5) with use cases; WP6: dissemination, community building, training and exploitation. WP1 drives the project (on tech viewpoint) WP7 on admin management</p> <p>Methods: performance optimisation and co-design</p>
<p><u>BioExcel-3</u></p>	<p><i>Centre of excellence for Computational Biomolecular Research</i></p>	<p><i>Supports computational molecular life sciences (neurosciences, drug discovery etc.) and developing exascale for life science. Provide researchers with high-quality user-friendly software, to increase their expertise and skills. Codes world leading open-source software like GROMACS, HADDOCK...</i></p>	<p>2 technical work-packages (core software and workflows), WP on user-driven development, WP on training and dissemination, WP on management. Industry interactions are part of the user-driven development as well as outreach and dissemination. One SME is a member of the consortium.</p>

<p><u>ESiWACE-3</u></p>	<p><i>Excellence in simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe</i></p>	<p><i>Focus on supporting the modelling community to reach a higher TRL for exascale supercomputing and foster knowledge transfer in EU.</i></p> <p><i>Objective: evolution: enable leading EU weather and climate models to leverage performance of pre-exascale systems, revolution: make use of exascale.</i></p>	<p>3 pillars: scalability of codes and of software development, usability of workflows in HPC environment and exploitability of data. Pillar 2 includes community building with regards to earth system modelling</p> <p>Pillar 1: WP1, 2, 3, about tech development. Pillar 2: WP4, 5, 6 about services and networking with community. WP5 => training & capacity building Partners, includes industry company Atos!</p> <p>Core services => infrastructures => R&I => Community engagement</p>
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Table 2: Goals and structure

CoE	COE-TYPE	Provision of services	Existing services Portal
EXCELLERAT P2	Type 2	Yes	https://services.excellerat.eu/
CEEC	Type 1	No	-
HiDALGO2	Type 2	Yes , provision of solution access to SMEs. 4 families of applications and 2 are directly targeting industry, there are also potential for industry with regard to their applications, or the general used techniques	-
ChEESE2	Type 2	Yes , mainly focused on the public sector.	-
MaX3	Type 1	Max3 did offer a set of services for expert users from industry in the past, it is not their current highest priority	http://www.max-centre.eu/services
SPACE	Type 1	No	-
MultiXScale	Type 2	In some way: Training yes, otherwise not directly. Cloud providers are providing apps SW- as- services to their users (customers)	-
Plasma-PEPSC	Type 1	No	-
BioExcel-3	Type 2	Yes , but any details to be discussed case-by-case	https://bioexcel.eu/services/
ESiWACE-3	Type 2	Maybe very indirectly by Meteo Centres / DestinE)	https://www.esiwace.eu/services

Table 3: Provision of services & Services portal

“Business” Marketing trainings

(1) “How to sell products[..]” with NCC Austria on March 30th, 2023

To address the need of understanding of “how to sell services to start-ups and SMEs “among the NCCs, CASTIEL2-WP4 organised a workshop “How to sell High Tech Products and Services“ and what we can learn from Tech-Startups” with NCC Austria on March 30th, 2023.

Following this workshop, an Autumn academy on the business development and marketing topic started to be in discussion with NCC Austria, CASTIEL-WP3 and the PMT to be organised during fall-winter 2023.

(2) Autumn academy set-up with NCC Austria: “Innovation and customer-users centric approached and mindset”

Following the workshop on “How to sell High Tech Products and Services “, and the interest of the participants to get hands-on information and training on this topic, a concept for an Autumn academy on the business development and marketing topic was developed by CASTIEL2-WP4 and NCC Austria, with support from the PMT during spring-summer 2023 to take place during fall-winter 2023. 19 representatives (from 15 NCCs and 2 CoEs) registered to participate to this Autumn academy that was launched by an online Survey produced by TheVentury in interaction with CASTIEL2-WP4 in September 2023, then an on-site workshop in Vienna on November 16th -17th 2023 (13 present participants on-site), followed by 2 online workshops during Winter 2023-2024. The details of the concept of this Autumn Academy co-developed with the marketing experts TheVentury and NCC Austria are presented in Annex 5. Pictures from the first on-site event are available in Figure 4.

**Figure 4: Group of participants from NCCs and CoEs that attended this on-site workshop.
Wall of multiple contributions (coloured post-it to address key questions)**

The feedbacks about this workshop were very positive as one can see from the Figure 5. The detailed answers to the complete feedbacks survey are presented in Annex 5. The ideas for further future workshops or actions on this generic topic “Marketing & sales” will be taken into

account to continue providing the NCCs and the CoEs with the most relevant skills, to address their specific challenges to interact with industry.

Figure 5: Feedback survey - satisfaction with this first on-site workshop

Additionally, some participants indicated several days after the on-site workshop, that they practically tested the learned mindset and approaches after being back in their respective NCCs with positive outcomes: see for instance the Belgium meeting about some methods discussed during the Vienna workshop and proposed for use in NCC Belgium in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Practical implementation in NCC Belgium of a method regarding marketing & customer-user, discussed in the Autumn academy in November 2023

(3) Marketing “sales” seminar with NCC Sweden

CASTIEL-WP4 and NCC Sweden started interacting after the Industry working group meeting in Stuttgart in February 2023 about a Marketing “sales” seminar to train the industry champions on how to shape best and how to sell their services provided by the NCCs to the industry stakeholders, with a focus on the “language for customers”. This action is currently planned for first semester of 2024.

(4) EuroCC Supercomputer Accelerator with NCC Austria

This task force, initiated by NCC Austria and supported by CASTIEL2-WP4, gathering 21 NCCs (list in Annex 6) was launched on September 7th 2023, with the presentation of the plan and timeline by NCC Austria. The plan was to distribute among all interested NCCs the requests from start-ups and SMEs received through EuroCC ACCESS or through the platform F6S (see the concept in Figure 7).

Figure 7: Concept of the "EuroCC Supercomputer Accelerator"

The added value of this task force is to launch common collaborative marketing actions to widely disseminate about the NCCs services and to join forces to address more requests from the start-ups willing to use HPC/HPDA/AI (HPC+) through the NCCs (in a way, this process being an improved version of the cluster tool developed during phase 1 of CASTIEL-EuroCC), see the screenshot of the landing page created by this task force to welcome the requests from start-ups and SMEs in Figure 8, with the application form available online².

² Landing page of the EuroCC Supercomputer Accelerator: <https://www.eurocc-access.eu/supercomputing-accelerator/>

The screenshot shows a landing page for an open call. At the top, a teal banner contains the text: "OPEN CALL EuroCC Supercomputing Accelerator --- Free service package for startups and SMEs to optimise computing tasks and grow with advanced technology". Below the banner are two buttons: "APPLY HERE" and "APPLY ON F65". The main content area has a light blue background and includes the following text and elements:

- Need more compute power to train AI models, analyse big data or run simulations?
- Want to stay ahead of the competition by using advanced computing technologies?

Apply for the EuroCC Supercomputing Accelerator and get an opportunity to grow your business while saving up to €76,000!

Why supercomputing?

With supercomputing, or high-performance computing (HPC), you can drastically accelerate computing tasks, reduce time-to-market of your product and optimise data-intensive computations such as training machine learning models.

More and more companies worldwide invest in expensive HPC infrastructure, but you don't have to: the European Union is publicly funding HPC access for startups and small and medium enterprises (SMEs), making it possible to use powerful national supercomputing infrastructure for commercial applications.

What do you get?

Supercomputing Accelerator offers you transfer of valuable HPC know-how tailored to your specific domain of science or industry. By applying for the EuroCC service package, you get:

- ✓ Tech feasibility check
- ✓ HPC training
- ✓ Business plan advice
- ✓ Financing advice
- ✓ Programming support
- ✓ Project support
- ✓ Access to supercomputers
- ✓ Link to experts

Powered by the Europe-wide network of HPC professionals from more than 30 countries, the EuroCC team will help you find effective solutions and integrate state-of-the-art technology into a successful business model. Apply now!

The following services are free of charge for the selected participants of the open call.

Figure 8: Screenshot of the landing page to welcome requests from start-ups and SMEs to the EuroCC2 network

This task force is a useful complementary action to the LinkHPC task force. The EuroCC Supercomputer Accelerator is indeed a program to welcome, train and support the early users of HPC+ (namely start-ups and SMEs), that could for instance develop their services thanks to HPC+. Then when these users/potential providers are ready, thanks to the Accelerator, they can go to the LinkHPC platform to use it as a stage to promote their services, their offers or to look for further specific HPC+ expertise or existing services. At end of November 2023, 9 types of services were available and more than 30 applications from start-ups or SMEs were received

through this F6S platform. These applications are currently being distributed among the NCCs part of this task force to address them and potentially provide services to new industry stakeholders.

3.4 Plans for the Next Steps

The current plan – that still might evolve given the outcomes of the ongoing task forces related to the industry topics and given the feedbacks of the first-year review to take place in February 2023 – is that CASTIEL2-WP4 would work, during 2024, on developing a central hub for the LinkHPC platform to be designed and articulated with the C2ISS and with the future national LinkHPC platforms. This will be done by:

- using on one side, the agreed common improved template/architecture skeleton of a LinkHPC platform for the national marketplaces (outcome expected by beginning of 2024)
- and on the other side the information collected from the CoEs and the NCCs about the central hub through the questionnaire used in 2023.

This being done in continuous interaction with WP5 in charge of the C2ISS.

“Business” Training of the NCCs and CoEs and support to them regarding the topic “marketing/sales” will be continued through the organisation of a marketing “sales” seminar with NCC Sweden and with potential other actions, using the needs reported by the NCCs and the CoEs through the various actions done in year 1.

The work performed through the “EuroCC Supercomputer Accelerator” task force will be continued and developed, potentially including even more NCCs or with the development of new features or processes.

Lastly, in collaboration with Task 4.3, a series of meetings for the NCCs to present their SMEs use cases/success stories to show how the NCCs supported the SMEs, and the benefits for them, could be organised by industry sector in a format similar to the Code of the Month activity, but this would be structured by industry sector: 1 volume per month or bi-monthly on one sector, the NCCs-CoEs would invite their SMEs contacts to present a few selected use cases during a 1-2-hour slot.

4 Task 4.2 “NCCs, CoEs – Industry Interaction Support”

4.1 Objectives and Strategy Implementation for Task 4.2

Task 4.2 is in charge of offering coordination to maximise the impact and to support further development of the CoE offerings by identifying and implementing actions to increase the volume of NCCs’ and CoEs’ engagement with industry.

Coordination and support of the NCCs and CoEs on these topics are done through the organisation of actions related to sectorial industry events of interest, potential thematic webinars and Code of the Month series.

4.2 Actions Undertaken During Year 1 and Results

Sectorial industry events of interest

(1) for the CoEs

Initially, the plan was to organise common participation to sectorial industry events with the CoEs, following the processes successfully used during the previous CSA FocusCoE. However, given that some CoEs were either just re-starting a new phase with new objectives towards industry or other stakeholders, or that other were starting from scratch with not specific elements to promote yet, or, as is the case for several CoEs (see the previous Table 2), no specific resources and objectives for targeting industry specifically are present, it appeared in spring 2023 that this approach would not lead to a very meaningful outcome at least in the short term. Therefore, it was decided to organise such common participation to sectorial industry events with the NCCs as prime contacts, and then to invite the CoEs to join the events that could be interesting for them.

(2) for the NCCs

As described above, following a new plan, CASTIEL2-WP4 contacted the NCCs, and in interaction with them set up a list of sectorial events of interest through all Europe. Consolidating the votes of the NCCs and having in mind the very limited budget of CASTIEL2 to support this action (23 000€) and the high price of booths (sometimes up to around 10-15 k€ for basic options) or other participation at such events, the events that received more than 5 votes were kept in a total list of potentially 10 events (details available in Annex 7). This list is used to prepare a joined and coordinated participation of the NCCs (and if interested, relevant CoEs) to the selected events. Given the very high prices of participation in some countries (for instance, in France), there are ongoing discussions to find some agreements with the national NCCs to foster their collaboration with the other interested NCCs for some kind of joint participation as not all events will be possibly funded by CASTIEL2-WP4. Each CASTIEL2-WP4 partner involved in T4.2 received several events to manage the events on behalf of CASTIEL2 with the responsibility to coordinate with the interested NCCs to organise a common participation to the sectorial event. CASTIEL2-WP4 providing when possible (i.e. with reasonable prices, rather around 3k€) the common booth and a few tickets for representatives of the NCCs to join and present their NCCs offers. Otherwise when the prices are too high, CASTIEL2-WP4 interacts with the national NCC to find alternative ways to involve the other NCCs.

Thematic outreach activities

During meetings of the WP4 CoE industry working group, it became clear that specific outreach to industry was not high on most CoEs current agendas. Thus, it was decided to broaden the

mission of WP4 somewhat regarding the support for CoEs to help them access user groups beyond their direct research community, which is evidently best address by themselves. In the previous CSA FocusCoE, good experience was made with thematic webinars on overarching topics. During the WG meetings, a few topics were identified where a coordinated approach to activities could bring an added value and increase visibility beyond the research communities addressed by the individual CoEs, in order to highlight potential services, offerings, perspectives and tools with potential to build awareness and prepare uptake in an entire area. One of the first areas is the broad field of “environmental simulation” covering the work of HiDALGO, ChEESE and ESiWACE. Their results could be useful for instance for environmental, urban or regional planning, disaster prevention and mitigation (such as wild fires, urban heat, regional implications of climate change etc.). In a first brainstorming meeting on September 28th 2023 with these CoEs, their view on this general approach and overall topic was gathered and first ideas for activities compiled. It became clear that a useful approach would likely not be limited to a singular event but a series of activities building the necessary awareness and connections. A first concrete goal envisaged is a workshop with interested NCCs who could contribute contacts to relevant players, such as public administrations interested in these applications and consulting companies in these areas.

Coordinated action to participate at events

Another kind of action to support the efforts of the NCCs to promote their offers is to coordinate a joint participation to international events like ISC2023. CASTIEL2-WP4 coordinated the participation of NCC Italy, NCC Croatia, NCC Türkiye at ISC2023 on May 24th 2023 for a BoF “HPC and industry cooperation in EU”, for them to present and promote their success stories and services. This participation allowed the NCCs to showcase their successful use cases and to meet potential prospects during the whole ISC2023 event. However, this will not be renewed for the next years, as the audience met at ISC2023 was mostly already about known entities or academic profiles.

“Code of the Month” series (in collaboration with WP2): 5 volumes

To promote the codes of the CoEs (i) towards the industry champions of the NCCs, for the NCCs to better present them in their country or to their potential prospects and (ii) towards the whole European ecosystem, CASTIEL2-WP4 and WP2 set-up a “Code of the Month” series.

For each series, there is an INTERNAL webinar only for industry and competence champions of the NCCs to allow informal discussions and specific questions, and there is a PUBLIC recorded webinar open to everyone. On 06.12.2023, 5 volumes were done and the next two others (with CEEC and BioExcel) are being scheduled. The details are provided in the Table 4 below.

	Code and CoE	Date of the webinars	Number of participants	Link to the recording
Volume 1	AVBP by EXCELLERAT-2	Internal on June 14 th 2023 Public on June 28 th 2023	30 participants 57 participants	https://www.eurocc-access.eu/services/video-library/
Volume 2	UAIF by RAISE	Internal on July 19 th 2023 Public on July 26 th 2023	28 participants 27 participants	

Volume 3	NekRS by CoEC	Internal on September 20 th 2023 Public on September 27 th 2023	24 participants 30 participants	
Volume 4	PhysiCell-X by PerMedCoE	Internal on November 8 th and Public on November 15 th	21 participants 9 participants	
Volume 5	EESSI by MultiXScale	Internal on November 28 th 2023 Public version will be covered by the long tutorial organised by CASTIEL2-WP3 on December 5 th 2023	33 participants Public version common with WP3 long tutorial.	

Table 4: “Code of the Month” series (in collaboration with WP2): 5 volumes by end of November 2023

4.3 Plans for the Next Steps

During the next period, the Code of the Month activity will be continued to become a well-established event and building a library of interesting short videos on a variety of high-end software.

The first joint industrial events will be attended, the first one being the “Innovation 4 Health” exhibition on March 28 in Rotterdam, and several more in the pipeline for 2024. It will also be explored what collaborations regarding industrial outreach can be established with the project coming out of Call DIGITAL-EUROHPC-JU-2023-SME-01-01.

The approach of thematic outreach activities will be pursued with the common topic of environmental simulation and extended to more topics, also including new CoEs as they become active.

5 Task 4.3 “NCCs – CoEs Exchange and Knowledge – Sharing on Industry Interactions”

5.1 Objectives and Strategy Implementation for Task 4.3

Task 4.3 is in charge of ensuring that both NCCs and CoEs have access to all relevant industrial interaction information and existing solutions, by organizing exchange and discussions about the lessons learned, by optimizing outreach and promotion activities of the NCCs towards industry and by involving other EC or EuroHPC JU funded R&I projects where advantageous (in collaboration with WP1).

5.2 Actions Undertaken During Year 1 and Results

To address the variety of the NCCs maturity, but also the variety of the NCCs needs and challenges, or the fact that different NCCs have different staff resources available or different levels of expertise available in their structure, CASTIEL2-WP4 decided to support all the initiatives that were developing collaboratively relevant tools potentially pre-existing in some NCCs or processes to assess the maturity of the SMEs (as potential prospects, to become users or customers of the NCCs services). This way, the NCCs needing to put in place tools or processes in their NCCs in order to better welcome prospects or to monitor their interactions with SMEs and industry stakeholders can select the solution the most relevant to their specific situation: an NCC meeting a lot of prospects through conferences or industry events can use the HPC4SME tool as a first meeting tool and follow-up later on; an NCC having a developed industry department and several experts on numerous topics can use the process developed in NCC Türkiye to select with which SMEs to interact, finally an NCC not knowing where to meet SMEs and start-ups and how to communicate can leverage the “EuroCC Supercomputer accelerator” (presented in Section (4)3.3) to get more SMEs and start-ups requests and address these as new contacts.

In this task 4.3 of “sharing the existing knowledge and best practices”, potentially developed in phase 1, we present the outcomes of the task force “HPC4SMEs” led by NCC Slovenia, the sharing done by NCC Türkiye about their white paper, then we report about the other actions done within this task in favour of best practices sharing and dissemination of useful content.

“SMEs assessment tool” task force led and managed by ARCTUR

This task force was launched in March 2023 with the lead by NCC Slovenia, in collaboration with CASTIEL2-WP2 and WP4, following some discussions and needs spotted during the kick-off meeting in Stuttgart. NCC Slovenia worked collectively with volunteer NCCs to improve their SMEs assessment tool, translate it in several languages and implement it in several NCCs. The tool improved and developed in 9 languages by NCC Slovenia and the task force members was finalised and online³ in September-October 2023 and the official announcement to the whole EUROCC network, with promotion of how to present this tool and how to potentially implement it in other countries, took place on November 29th 2023 during an online meeting.

³ HPC4SME tool: <https://aat.hpc4sme.eu/questionnaire/overview>

The concept reminded during this official launch announcement event by ARCTUR is summarised in in the slide of Figure 9 and in the process scheme in Figure 10.

Figure 9: HPC4SMEs concept

Figure 10: HPC4SMEs proposed process

Following the end of this task force, CASTIEL2-WP4 and WP2 worked on an online questionnaire to ask the task force members about their feedbacks in October 2023 (detailed report about them in Annex 8). Overall, the Task Force “SMEs assessment tool” is considered very successful by the Task Force members, by CASTIEL2 WP2 and WP4 and by NCC Slovenia who led the works. The way the Task Force operated was efficient and allowed to obtain a tangible result in a relatively short time. This action and the related outcome provided a new useful tool for the NCCs to interact with the SMEs, as explained in the presentation marketing document (see Annex 9) created by NCC Slovenia: “using the HPC4SME AAT gives an NCC the advantage in data-driven decision-making, strategic planning, and more. Secondly, the automatically generated reports and personalised recommendations generated by the HPC4SME Automated Assessment Tool (AAT) represent a potent information resource for your HPC4SME AAT’s end users, enabling them to chart their course with data-driven insights”.

The outcomes of this action were already useful for the NCCs by end of November 2023, as 17 NCCs either already contributed to have the tool usable by their potential SMEs prospects, or indicated their interest to use it. It was translated in 9 languages and planned for 1 more (French) in the next months and 33 assessments were already completed by SMEs in Europe.

Maturity assessment of the SMEs – white paper and collaboration proposal by NCC Türkiye

On August 29th 2023, CASTIEL2-WP4 invited NCC Türkiye to present their white paper "Development of a maturity assessment tool to improve SME HPC capabilities" to the industry working group of the NCCs. NCC Türkiye developed indeed a process to assess the maturity of the SMEs they interact with for the first time. This process is done through interviews, assessments by experts within their NCC. The details are presented and explained in their white paper available online⁴ on EuroCC ACCESS website. During this meeting, NCC Türkiye presented their process and offered to the other NCCs to collaborate with them in case they would be interested to implement similar processes in their NCC.

Industry coffee breaks

The purpose of this action is to provide a space of free informal discussions, and to discuss important topics and collect direct feedbacks, questions or needs from the industry champions. Virtual industry coffee breaks were organised on July 6th, September 28th, and October 26th 2023, November 23st 2023, December 21st 2023. The virtual coffee breaks allowed industry champions to exchange ideas, to ask CASTIEL2-WP4 about needed elements, actions or clarifications.

Industry success stories booklet (in collaboration with WP5) & industry use-cases portfolio

In the continuity of the work done during phase 1, CASTIEL2-WP4 kept interacting with WP5 to produce an industry success stories booklet⁵ in May 2023. This booklet was first distributed during ISC2023 in Hamburg. Then it was also published online for a wide promotion .

Additionally, starting in September 2023, CASTIEL2-WP4 interacted with NCC Belgium to produce a template for a slides deck (a “portfolio”) of industry use cases. The “November 2023” version of this living-document/template is available in Annex 10. Ten NCCs provided 26 use cases from 11 industry sectors (out of a list of 28 industry sectors) by October 2023. On

⁴ White paper by NCC Türkiye: <https://www.eurocc-access.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/07/White-paper-v1.0.pdf>

⁵ EuroCC2 booklet n°1: https://www.eurocc-access.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/07/EuroCC_booklet_2023_final.pdf

November 10th, a first complete portfolio either sorted by NCC names or by industry sectors was shared with all NCCs (see Annex 11). This portfolio will be regularly updated by CASTIEL2-WP4 when future use cases will be provided by the NCCs. The aim is indeed for the NCCs to be able to use it to interact with potential prospects from various industry sectors by showing them successful use cases from the relevant specific industry sector.

Webinars with other initiatives

When relevant, CASTIEL2-WP4 organised webinars for the industry champions to receive direct information from other initiatives, that could be relevant for their interactions with potential prospects or ongoing collaborations with industry. The webinars organised in 2023 were:

(1) FF4EuroHPC success stories - alignment with CASTIEL2 (WP4) webinar on April 24th 2023

This webinar was the opportunity for the industry champions to hear about the outcomes of the open calls of FF4EuroHPC, about statistics regarding them, and to hear useful tips to prepare successful applications for future similar open calls.

(2) ETP4HPC: presentation of their market study results in July 2023

As the NCCs were asked to participate to the ETP4HPC market study in Summer 2022, ETP4HPC presented some first results and outcomes of this study to the industry champions in July 2023.

(3) Interaction with GAIA-X and EDIHs to organize a webinar with them for the NCCs and CoEs by end of 2023.

GAIA-X presented its objectives and opportunities during a webinar on November 6th 2023. A workshop with the EDIHS is yet to be organised. Since this touches other areas and the concept needs to be well thought out with all stakeholders, this is postponed.

5.3 Plans for the Next Steps

The continuous work about the industry success stories will be continued in collaboration with WP5, the NCCs and as new collaborators the CoEs too. Indeed, a second booklet is planned for Summer 2024, and either this new volume will include industry success stories from the CoEs too, or there will be a dedicated booklet for the CoEs. Similarly, the continuous work about the industry use cases portfolio will be continued in collaboration with the NCCs, with the aim by the end of the EUROCC2 project to have collected use cases from all industry sectors and from all NCCs.

The industry coffee breaks will continue as they allow the industry champions from NCCs and CoEs to interact together; this is also an opportunity for them to ask questions to CASTIEL2-WP4 or to formulate needs or requests for some specific actions or support.

At the beginning of 2024, the NCCs will be asked about the organisations or entities they have been connected yet and Task 4.3 will analyse if the most relevant actors have been covered. Then, to reinforce the knowledge about the industry stakeholders in the HPC ecosystem in Europe, there will be topic-focused meetings with some relevant initiatives per topic (e.g. funding for SMEs, infrastructure access etc.). This way, the NCCs and the CoEs would have opportunity to interact with HPC actors outside of the European ecosystem, and that are relevant regarding the industry topics to provide guidance for NCCs in the international ecosystem.

6 Transversal Topics Monitored by Work Package 4

There are several topics that are transversal to all tasks of WP4. They are therefore organised and monitored centrally, and the results and outcomes are made available to all tasks leaders.

6.1 Key Figures Regarding Interactions with Industry

- **For the NCCs**

In continuity with phase 1 of EuroCC/CASTIEL that ended on December 2022, the project management team (PMT) collects quarterly Technical Progress Reports (TPRs) from the NCCs. Following the end of the phase 1 of EuroCC/CASTIEL, CASTIEL-2-WP4 updated in the template of these TPRs the two tables about “Industry figures”.

The questions asked in these quarterly TPRs are indicated in the tables Table 5 and Table 6 below.

Industry Interaction – SMEs within the reported 3-month period

	Last up-to-date figures FOR THIS QUARTER
Number of PoCs done with SME	X PoCs done with SMEs
Projects initiated with SMEs ⁶	X projects initiated
Projects finalised with SMEs ⁷	X projects finalised
Sectors concerned ⁸	X sectors concerned
Number of success stories with SMEs	X success stories ready for publication & shared with CASTIEL2

Table 5: Industry interaction with SMEs

Industry Interaction – Big Industry (Large companies) within the reported 3-month period

	Last up-to-date figures FOR THIS QUARTER
Number of PoCs done with Big Industry stakeholders	X PoCs done with Big Industry stakeholders
Projects initiated with Big Industry ⁹	X projects initiated
Projects finalised with Big Industry ¹⁰	X projects finalised
Sectors concerned ¹¹	X sectors concerned
Number of success stories with Big Industry	X success stories ready for publication & shared with CASTIEL2

Table 6: Industry interaction with Big Industry

6 e.g. All other types of projects, that are not PoCs (e.g., support provided to submit a proposal to a funding agency OR collaboration agreement/MoU signed, etc.)

7 e.g. All other successful types of projects, that are not PoCs (e.g., funding grant received by SME thanks to NCC support OR technology transfer support, etc.)

8 looking at the list from the ILO

9 e.g. All other types of projects, that are not PoCs (e.g., collaboration or contract initiated between a Big Industry player and the NCC, etc.)

10 e.g. All other types of projects, that are not PoCs (e.g., successful finished collaboration with a Big Industry player or finished direct contracts, etc.)

11 looking at the list from the ILO

The results for the first two quarters (Q1: January-March 2023 and Q2: April-June 2023) were collected by the PMT and forwarded to CASTIEL-2-WP4. CASTIEL-2-WP4 processed these figures, the results are presented in Annex 12.

Looking at the very low reported numbers and at the high amount of “no answer”, CASTIEL2-WP4 interacted with the industry champions of the NCCs on October 12th 2023 to understand where there might have been some miscommunication or confusion and to ensure that the objectives of the tables (i.e. for CASTIEL2 to monitor the evolution of the interactions of the NCCs with industry stakeholders) were understood. Afterwards, CASTIEL2-WP4 produced a FAQ document (Annex 13) to explain how to fill in these tables and how to properly count and declare PoCs and projects in the NCCs. This way, the next quarters should allow CASTIEL2 to have a better view of the actions undertaken by the NCCs to interact with industry (through PoCs and projects).

- **For the CoEs:** in C5, it was decided during September-October 2023, at the request of CASTIEL2-WP4, that PMT will collect the same industry figures from the CoEs when the Collaboration Agreement (COLA) will have been signed between them and CASTIEL2 (this being not yet in place by December 8th 2023).

6.2 Meetings and Workshops for the Industry Working Group

Several meetings of the industry working group were organised as transversal actions (between the three tasks of WP4), as they promoted outcomes of transversal actions or as they were meant to provide valuable inputs for phase 2 for all tasks of WP4 to work on their specific topics. These meetings are listed in the Table 7.

Title	Objective	Date & Location	Content-Outcomes of the meeting
Industry working group meeting: “Lessons learned from phase 1 & launch of phase 2”	To collect the feedbacks following the end of phase 1 and to start the phase 2 with relevant feedbacks and new requests from the industry champions	January 31 st 2023 Stuttgart, Germany	Collection of key topics for the NCCs, for CASTIEL2-WP4 to implement actions to address them during EUROCC2-CASTIEL2
Industry working group meeting “kick-off meeting”	Session organised during the kick-off meeting, to launch the phase 2 and discuss the plans regarding the industry working group	February 07 th 2023 Stuttgart, Germany	The objectives set up in the various Grant Agreements (EUROCC2-CASTIEL2) were discussed. The interactions with the CoEs, new members of EUROCC2 -CASTIEL2 were discussed
Industry working group at the CoEs kick-off meeting organised by CASTIEL2-WP2	Participation to the CoEs kick-off meeting organised by CASTIEL2-WP2	April 18 & 19th 2023, online	Organisation of an “Industry topics” session, with animation of group discussions and monitoring of a concept-board used to collect the goals, challenges and needs of the NCCs & CoEs with regards to the industry topics during this starting period of EuroCC2-CASTIEL2
Cluster tool tutorial (updates & how to use it)	Session co-organised with CASTIEL2-WP5	May 16th 2023, online	Meeting online to update the NCCs about how to enter their info, and how to use it, and about the available external contact page
Industry working group meeting to launch a task force on the topic “LinkHPC platform”	Meeting to present the current situation, the lack of feedbacks from the review of CASTIEL1 on this topic, and to propose to create a task force to at least create a common template for such a platform.	June 29th 2023, online	To present the proposal by CASTIEL2-WP4 to work together on the “LinkHPC topic” & set up a dedicated task force

Table 7: Meetings organised transversally by CASTIEL2-WP4

7 Major Achievements and Concluding Remarks

During the first year of the CASTIEL-2 project, WP4 performed various and numerous actions. Major achievements for CASTIEL2-WP4 for the benefit of the NCCs are the various outcomes and results performed by the task forces, coordinated by CASTIEL2-WP4:

- “LinkHPC platform: design of a common structure for the services” led by NCC France (see details in section 3.2)
- “EuroCC Supercomputer accelerator” led by NCC Austria (see details in section 3.3)
- “SMEs assessment tool” led by NCC Slovenia (see details in section 5)

Thanks to these task forces, during this first year 2023, there were several valuable developments of tools, processes and templates that can then be used by the whole EUROCC2 network.

CASTIEL2-WP4 also organised for the industry champions (and the communication or competence champions on some actions) dedicated customised trainings on the topic “marketing/sales” (see details in section 3.3), in order for the NCCs and CoEs to be able to properly present and promote their services towards industry stakeholders.

Other major outcomes, including summary documents and provided information, are:

- (1) Information about the “pay-per-use” access for industry to the EuroHPC-JU supercomputers

Following the meeting of the industry working group in Stuttgart in January 2023 (details about this meeting in Table 7) and the request made there by the NCCs to receive clear information about how industry can get access through “pay-per-use” to the JU supercomputers, CASTIEL2-WP4 undertook an investigation on this topic and produced in July 2023 a summary Guide regarding Access for Industry to EuroHPC JU Systems, publicly available at https://www.eurocc-access.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/07/202307_Access-to-supercomputers-of-the-JU_Industry_focus.pdf.

- (2) Information about the CoEs, with regards to their interaction with industry

Following the online kick-off meeting organised for the CoEs by CASTIEL2-WP2 on April 18 & 19th 2023 CASTIEL2-WP4 produced a detailed report about the main information about the CoEs, their interactions with industry and their structure in a detailed report was produced about these topics and shared only internally with all the NCCs and the CoEs (see **Annex 4, only shared with the JU and the reviewers**). Public tables, summarising their goals and structure (Table 2), and summarising the information regarding provision of services by the CoEs (Table 3) were also provided to the NCCs and CoEs for dissemination to potential prospects about the opportunities offered by the CoEs.

- (3) Sharing of “EU” information

Continuing what was done during EUROCC1/CASTIEL1, CASTIEL2-WP4 kept regularly forwarding by email to the industry champions the information received about the EU (JU/EC or even outside the Horizon Europe) about potential funding or opportunities for industry that could be of interest for the NCCs or the CoEs.

8 References

- [1] GUIDE || Access for Industry to EuroHPC JU Systems: <https://www.eurocc-access.eu/services/document-library/>
- [2] Landing page of the EuroCC Supercomputer Accelerator: <https://www.eurocc-access.eu/supercomputing-accelerator/>
- [3] HPC4SME tool: <https://aat.hpc4sme.eu/questionnaire/overview>
- [4] White paper by NCC Türkiye: <https://www.eurocc-access.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/07/White-paper-v1.0.pdf>
- [5] EuroCC2 booklet n°1: https://www.eurocc-access.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/07/EuroCC_booklet_2023_final.pdf

9 Annexes

Annex 1: Report “LinkHPC platform Articulation with the C2SSI”

Annex 2: a) NCCs members of the task force "Test of LinkHPC platform to design a services structure" & b) extract of the form to collect the task force members feedback on the EN test version of the “CC-FR marketplace”

Annex 3: Information about the CoEs services portals

Annex 4: CONFIDENTIAL: CoEs and industry interactions (structure, key topics, objectives)

Annex 5: Autumn Academy concept, co-developed with TheVentury and NCC Austria & results of the feedbacks survey

Annex 6: NCCs members of the task force "EuroCC Supercomputer Accelerator"

Annex 7: consolidated list of industry sectorial events to be commonly attended with the NCCs & interested CoEs

Annex 8: Summary of the results of the feedback questionnaire “SMEs assessment tool”

Annex 9: Marketing strategy for the HPC4SME AAT NCC Slovenia

Annex 10: Template for the industry use-cases portfolio

Annex 11: First industry use cases portfolio sorted by industry sectors

Annex 12: Results of the NCCs TPRs for Q1 & Q2

Annex 13: FAQ Industry figures for the TPRs

Annex 1: Report “LinkHPC platform Articulation with the C2SSI”

DIGITAL-EUROHPC-JU-2022-NCC-01

LinkHPC platform Articulation with the C2SSI

Update from October 2023

Analytics collected through the questionnaire “C2SSI” organised by WP5 of CASTIEL with support of WP4 of CASTIEL. Answers provided by the NCCs from the EuroCC2 project & CoEs funded by the Calls HORIZON-EUROHPC-JU-2021-COE-01-01 and HORIZON-EUROHPC-JU-2021-COE-01-02

**Coordination & Support
for National Competence Centres on a European Level Phase 2
Project Number: 101102047**

EuroHPC
Joint Undertaking

This project has received funding from the European High-Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (JU) under grant agreement No 101102047. The JU receives support from the Digital Europe Programme and Germany, Italy, Spain, France, Belgium, Austria.

List of abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
CASTIEL2	Phase 2 of CASTIEL
C2ISS CASTIEL 2	Information Sharing System
CoE	Centre of Excellence
EC	European Commission
EuroCC2	Phase 2 of EuroCC
EuroHPC JU	The European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking
HPC	High-Performance Computing
HPDA	High-Performance Data Analytics
JU	Short version of EuroHPC Joint Undertaking
NCC	National Competence Centre
PoC	Proof of Concept
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
WP	Work Package

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1 Introduction

The CASTIEL2-WP5 team created during Spring 2023 a questionnaire to collect the NCCs and CoEs initial feedbacks with regards to the topic C2SSI - CASTIEL 2 Information Sharing System (more details in the deliverable D5.2 “Design Strategy of the C2ISS and the evolved EuroCC ACCESS Portal” submitted in September 2023). During the preparation of this questionnaire, CASTIEL2-WP4 collaborated with the WP5 for the part of the questionnaire that is about the future hub of the Marketplace/LinkHPC platform. This platform will be articulated with the C2SSI to collect updated information from the NCCs and the CoEs about the services and the information by or for industry.

5 CoEs and 19 NCCs provided feedbacks to this questionnaire by end of July 2023. The questionnaire included questions about the various topics/fields to be included in the C2SSI, and a specific section about the potential future hub of the LinkHPC Platform.

During October 2023, the parts of the questionnaire about the competences and about the future hub of the LinkHPC platform were re-opened by CASTIEL2-WP2 and WP4, in order to collect more feedbacks from the pool of the 10 CoEs, for a better representativity. At the end, 11 people from the 10 CoEs answered to the questionnaire.

This report presents the answers collected through this questionnaire for the questions about the Marketplace/LinkHPC platform. This report will be shared with the other WPs of CASTIEL, with the NCCs and with the JU (at least through the deliverable D4.1 to be submitted in December 2023), in order to provide an initial overview of the needs and suggestions of the CoEs and NCCs when it comes to the topic Marketplace/LinkHPC platform and to initiate the works on the design of this platform. This design will be done through the task force managed by WP4 named "Test of LinkHPC platform/marketplace to design a services structure". The task force will allow the WP4 team to refine the concepts first mentioned through this questionnaire and to clarify when necessary the sub-topics and various items.

2 Results of the questionnaire – part about the Marketplace/LinkHPC platform

2.1 Information visible, in terms of services

Figure 1: Interesting information to display in terms of services

All the proposed services look important for the majority of the NCCs to be displayed on the hub. For the CoEs, information about *Quantum computing* and about *Edge computing* look interesting only for one CoE.

2.2 Information visible, in terms of information about the national ecosystems

Figure 2: Interesting information to display in terms of national ecosystems

For the majority of the NCCs, all the proposed types of information about national ecosystems are interesting to be displayed on the hub, i.e. to be visible at the EU level. For the CoEs, their answers indicate that they would rather be interested in seeing information about *EU projects*, *research center profiles*, *individual person profiles* and *private companies' profiles*, but there is also some interest for all categories, even for “not displayed yet” categories (like Open source applications that the profiles contribute to, Research Area open for collaboration).

2.3 Information visible, in terms of events available

Figure 3: Interesting information to display in terms of events

For the majority of the NCCs, *workshops*, *webinars*, *hackathons* and *information sessions* would be the most interesting events to be displayed on the hub of the LINKHPC platform. For the CoEs, their answers are similar to the ones from the NCCs.

2.4 Information visible, in terms of other areas

Figure 4: Interesting information to display in terms of other areas

For the majority of the NCCs, *success stories and jobs* info must be displayed on the hub, i.e. to be visible at the EU level. For the CoEs, their answers are similar to the ones from the NCCs.

2.5 Information needed with regards to the codes

Figure 5: Interesting information to display in terms of codes

For the majority of the NCCs, information about *user support* and *consulting on code optimization* must be displayed on the hub, i.e. to be visible at the EU level. Then, several NCCs (between 3 and 5) would also like that information about *the codes (and services linked to them)*, *information about PoCs*, *workflows*, *datasets*, *trainings* is visible on the central hub. For the CoEs, they would only be interested in providing or seeing information about the *codes (and services linked to them)* and with less votes, also for all other types of information, except for PoCs.

2.6 Comments

A last question was:

“Which other features are important for you to have on the HUB of the "MARKETPLACE /EU-LinkHPC" platform (=central unique entry -point, simple overview of the EU oppportunities, in English)?”

The answers to this question are gathered in the **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.**

NCCs	CoEs
simple overview of the EU oppportunities	Multiple languages
Technology readiness level per item	Differences and Synergies between C2ISS and LinkHPC should be defined
Information about other HPC and other related technology projects outside of EuroCC/CASTIEL, which within the European Ecosystem	
not to create something new but to use something already developped into EUROCC for EUROCC like the French Marketplace	
Collaboration "match making" (NCC-NCC; NCC-CoE)	
codes (that have services linked to them), trainings on code usage, PoCs/ Test before Invest, Consulting on using codes for solving problems, Consulting on code optimization	

Table 1: Other comments

3 Conclusions

The results show that except for the codes, almost all the NCCs are generally interested in displaying and seeing every available information when it comes to services, the ecosystem, the events and the other areas.

The CoEs have a little more specific interests, for instance particularly on the codes and their related services, on training, consultancy and the external ecosystem.

To concretely assess the priorities and to better design the exact organization to present all these elements of information on the future hub of the Marketplace/LinkHPC platform, face to face discussions and use of an existing solution to be able to show and criticize in-depth will be useful within the future task force "Test of LinkHPC platform/marketplace to design a services structure".

Annex 2-a: NCCs members of the task force "Test of LinkHPC platform to design a services structure"

NCCs members of the task force "Test of LinkHPC platform to design a services structure"
FRANCE
SWEDEN
AUSTRIA
IRELAND
ICELAND
NETHERLANDS
SLOVENIA
BELGIUM
CROATIA
POLAND
TURKIYE
ESTONIA
SLOVENIA
SPAIN
GERMANY

Table 8: NCCs members of the task force "Test of LinkHPC platform to design a services structure"

Annex 2-b: Extract of the form to collect the task force members feedback on the EN test version of the “CC-FR marketplace”

Feedback of LINHPC Test Version			NCC involved into the Task Force										
Please read these practical guidelines before completing this document			AUSTRIA	BELGIUM	CROATIA	ESTONIA	GERMANY	ICELAND	IRELAND	NETHERLANDS	POLAND	SLOVAKIA	
<p>0: You are not alone :) if something is not clear or if you have a question or something is not clear about how to use of the test version, please send an email to katriin.scoum@teratic.fi and marie-francoise.gerard@teratic.eu</p> <p>1: Each NCC has a dedicated column to report the feedbacks, if different people from your NCC provide feedbacks, please report all of them in your unique NCC column.</p> <p>2: Regarding improvement or modification, provide for each request the priority from 0 (Not important) to 5 (Very important). Keep in mind that each improvement or modification needs development and has a cost</p> <p>3: Structure your feedback input in each section beginning by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> +Language correction; +Comment; +Modification: don't forget to give a Priority: 0 to 5 +Improvement: don't forget to give a Priority: 0 to 5 +Other (Please use an understanding label/name); 													
Structuration of your feedbacks by categories and sub categories													
Categories	Sub categories	Feedbacks categories											
1: Creation of an account (In general)		Language correction											
		Comment											
		Modification: don't forget to give a Priority: 0 to 5 Improvement: don't forget to give a Priority: 0 to 5 Other (Please use an understanding label/name);	Example: +First Feedbacks – priority 2 +Second Feedbacks – priority 0										
2: Access to the Marketplace (In general)		Language correction											
		Comment											
		Modification: don't forget to give a Priority: 0 to 5 Improvement: don't forget to give a Priority: 0 to 5 Other (Please use an understanding label/name);											
3: Creation of my account	Personal data	Language correction											
		Comment											
		Modification: don't forget to give a Priority: 0 to 5 Improvement: don't forget to give a Priority: 0 to 5 Other (Please use an understanding label/name);											
	Qualifications, skills & expertise	Language correction											
		Comment											
		Modification: don't forget to give a Priority: 0 to 5 Improvement: don't forget to give a Priority: 0 to 5 Other (Please use an understanding label/name);											
	Professional activity	Language correction											
		Comment											
		Modification: don't forget to give a Priority: 0 to 5 Improvement: don't forget to give a Priority: 0 to 5 Other (Please use an understanding label/name);											
	Your research and needs	Language correction											
		Comment											
		Modification: don't forget to give a Priority: 0 to 5 Improvement: don't forget to give a Priority: 0 to 5 Other (Please use an understanding label/name);											
Subscribe to the Competence Centre newsletter	Language correction												
	Comment												
	Modification: don't forget to give a Priority: 0 to 5 Improvement: don't forget to give a Priority: 0 to 5 Other (Please use an understanding label/name);												
Management of my personal data	Language correction												
	Comment												
	Modification: don't forget to give a Priority: 0 to 5 Improvement: don't forget to give a Priority: 0 to 5 Other (Please use an understanding label/name);												
Validating my account	Language correction												
	Comment												
	Modification: don't forget to give a Priority: 0 to 5 Improvement: don't forget to give a Priority: 0 to 5 Other (Please use an understanding label/name);												

Figure 11: Form to collect the task force members feedback on the EN test version of the “CC-FR marketplace”

Annex 3: Information about the CoEs services portals

Annex 4: CONFIDENTIAL- CoEs and industry interactions (structure, key topics, objectives)

Separated PDF – only for reviewers and JU

Annex 5: Autumn Academy concept, co-developed with TheVentury and NCC Austria & results of the feedbacks survey

EuroHPC
Joint Undertaking

Innovation (innovation & customer centric-marketing approaches) Autumn Academy

Organizer:

This Autumn school event would be a EuroCC2 -TheVentury-CASTIEL2 event.

It is organized by NCC Austria and The Ventury (Innovation agency, business consultants) with support from CASTIEL2.

Date and duration:

Online initial survey
then 1.5 days on site,
then 2 online half-days workshops
(with homework in between)
throughout Autumn-Winter 2023

Location:

The 1.5 days - event will take place at INiTS Home:
INiTS Universitäres Gründerservice Wien GmbH
Maria Jacobi Gasse 1., MQM 3.4., 5. Floor, 1030 Vienna.

Overview:

Innovation consultants from the Ventury will interact with the willing industry champions of the NCCs and the CoEs to understand their needs with regards to innovation (in terms of a **basic knowledge** of innovation & customer centric-marketing approaches), to exchange and share with them the fundamental basis for innovation mindset and practical methods, ready to use, then to follow-up the hands-on and (a little longer-term) real-life homework in the respective NCCs/CoEs teams throughout Autumn-Winter 2023.

Description:

- i) The interested participants (1 per NCC/CoE maximum) will have to do some preparation upfront: they will be asked to fill in the initial online questionnaire that will help The Ventury to frame the NCCs/CoEs status and their commonalities to be leveraged during the onsite 1.5 days,
- ii) then, there will be the kick-off onsite event with various sessions and workshops during 1.5 days
- iii) then they will have real-life homework to see how to practically apply in their respective national/project teams the methods discussed during the onsite event, and
- iv) the 2 planned online follow-up workshops will allow feedbacks between the participants and the Ventury, with answering of practical questions.

This will ensure practical and long-lasting impact for all participants.

Learning by doing (during and between the workshop days) is the core of this concept.

Target audience:

The willing industry champions of the NCCs and the CoEs
And a priori around 20 people given the first surveys done to ask for potential interest (during some previous events of Castiel2-EuroCC2).
UPDATE 19.10.2023: 21 registered participants to the whole Autumn academy

Prerequisite knowledge for the participants:

To be involved in the industry topics, more particularly the marketing ones for the NCC or the CoE, i.e. for the participant, to be actively working with industry or aiming to work with industry, and potential users or clients.

Workflow:

Initial online survey for all participants (in September-October 2023)
On-site event for 1.5 days organized by the innovation experts of TheVentury
2 online workshops (with 3-4 weeks in between to allow the participants to test and apply the methods in their respective teams)

In details: the Academy-journey is structured in three main parts (*adaption may occur after survey results*):

- **1) Kick-Off Workshop** (1.5 days, on-site): *focus on Workmode, lean and agile methods, product & service development, Hypothesis driven framework, ideation*
- 2-3 weeks: Work on tasks in teams: *build upon those ideas, building a prototype*
- **2) Customer Centric Workshop** (0.5 days, online): *focus on customer centricity, interviews, co-creating with customers, Stakeholder management & map*
- 3-4 weeks: Work on tasks in teams: *conducting interviews, insights and validating hypotheses*
- **3) Product Marketing Workshop** (0.5 days, online): *focus on “how to” marketing and validation, what does “marketing & sales” mean in EuroCC context: what are the skills the participants need, “go to market/customer”-strategies + clear Actions & To Dos*

Figure 1: Proposed timeline and milestones

Skills to be gained:

At the end of the whole event/process the NCC or CoE representative will be able to test and apply (and ask questions, if need be, following these concrete tests) professional methods to ensure user-customer centricity and experience, and collaboration with other teams to foster common tools or services offers among the NCCs and CoEs.

Following the initial survey, The Ventury will also provide and customize the most relevant learning environment focussing on the priority topics for the participants with regards to marketing/innovation mindsets and methods.

Provisional agenda :

- **Thursday 16 Nov :**
 - Check-in at 8.30 am
 - **starting 9.00** am CET to 12.00,
 - 1hour lunch break,
 - 1pm to 6.30pm (with breaks in between)
 - 7.30pm: dinner organized commonly
- **Friday 17 Nov :**
 - Check-in 9.00
 - Starting 9.30am to 1.00 pm (incl. coffee breaks)
END at 1.00 pm

At date 19.10.2023: 21 registered participants from 15 NCCs and 2 CoEs.

Summary of the results of the feedback survey

Autumn academy

“Innovation and customer-users centric approached and mindset”

EuroHPC
Joint Undertaking

This project has received funding from the European High-Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (JU) under grant agreement No 101102047. The JU receives support from the Digital Europe Programme and Germany, Italy, Spain, France, Belgium, Austria.

Introduction

The concept for an Autumn school on the business development and marketing topic was developed by CASTIEL2-WP4 and NCC Austria, with support from the PMT during Spring-Summer 2023 to take place during Fall-Winter 2023.

19 representatives (from 15 NCCs and 2 CoEs) registered to participate to this Autumn academy that was launched by an online Survey produced by TheVentury in interaction with CASTIEL2-WP4 in September 2023, then an on-site workshop in Vienna on November 16th -17th 2023 (13 present participants on-site), followed by 2 online workshops during Winter 2023-2024.

Following the end of the on-site workshop, a feedback survey was created by WP4 to collect feedback on how the workshop went and the needs for the next steps. The survey was shared with the participants on November 17th 2023 and 8 answers were collected. This document is a summary of the answers.

Analysis of results

Question 1: What is your overall satisfaction with the outcomes of this first on-site workshop? [ranking from "Bad" to "Excellent"]

The overall satisfaction with the outcomes of the Task Force is **good**, as 6 out of 8 people indicated it and the two others even reported it as **excellent**.

Question 2: What did you like or what was particularly useful for you?

The following comments were given as open answers in the questionnaire:

1. The Methods for Desk Research / Testing your hypothesis.
2. Connecting with people from other NCCS and building relationships for the work that is to come.
3. Learning about how other NCCs are working
4. The Ventury team have a lot of experience and are very knowledgeable

Exchange and network with our European colleagues face to face. I take home some concrete actions or changes that I can immediately implement in my daily work.

The hands-on and the exchange between NCC/CoEs

Meeting other in the same role as me

I particularly enjoyed DAY 2 where we started testing theory applying it directly to the EURO CC challenges

Practical case studies in addition to theoretical foundations

Real discussions on how to approach our audience and learn about other NCCs best practices

Face-to-face interactions and discussions and experience sharing between NCCs

Question 3: What could be improved or added for the next steps (online workshops & homework) of this Autumn academy?

The following comments were given as open answers in the questionnaire:

The next online workshop could: "offer the stage" to every NCC to share their experience so far with validating the hypothesis, but in a structured manner
> making use of Mentimeter + setting online etiquette for how ways of interacting (i.e. raise hand & wait of your name to be called) and proper timing.

Focus on EuroCC situation and goals a bit more.

I can't think of something! All worked very nice!

There must be provided more time between workshops, so that homework can be conducted properly

I think that theory could be enriched with use cases and techniques that are more tailored to our specific challenge. Therefore a high-tech niche B2B sale. It is interesting to know about B2C techniques but we need to draw inspiration from more specific marketing best practices that can be applied in our field.

More useful tools
How to make HPC attractive for our audience by emails and social media posts
Presentations/Walkthroughs of best practices (e.g. in how to use best dissemination process/tools etc)

Question 4: Do you have comments or suggestions for CASTIEL2 with regards to this action?

The following comments were given as open answers in the questionnaire:

I would be happy to take the lead - [-] (NCC [-]) - and organise a next online workshop where we facilitate the knowledge exchange between NCCs in a structured way: focusing on do's & dont's, successful practices and lessons learned.
Thanks for supporting the workshop, it adds value to EuroCC.
Even though it's hard to convince them, a lot of experts could use seminars like this
Set the dates in advance so that we know when the workshops are due
Not specifically, I think it's about challenging the consulting agency to really dig deep into this high-tech niche openers and see what examples and techniques they can suggest.
Some adaptations to COEs particularities
Organise similar initiatives for the future and involve all NCCs in it. I believe that this coaching companies are very valuable for collaboration between NCCs.
Good that only one flight was necessary to get to venue.

Question 5: What would be the other needs linked to Marketing & sales that you would know want to learn or experiment in such a collaborative format?

The following comments were given as open answers in the questionnaire:

World Cafe Reloaded :). Let me know if you need any help with hosting it - happy to do so. :)
Use of Tools (e.g. LinkedIn sales, good CRMs, etc), have a concrete concerted action that implements some of the working methods (agile, lean, etc). E.g. in the supercomputer accelerator, or in another industry project. We need to keep collaborating on a European level to make this work.
Lead creation

I would like to know more about how other NCC work to follow up leads and how they build a portfolio of prospective clients

The **unique selling points of our HPC centers, versus that of commercial providers**. We often get that question from customers as well as funding agencies, and others: for the NCCs to better explain how we differ from commercial providers such as AWS, Azure, GCP, etc

-

Best practices guides

Marketing pipeline servicing, online workshop on dissemination message testing

Conclusions

Overall, the Autumn academy whole concept and this particular on-site workshop went very well.

The NCCs learned useful concepts (methods, tools, ideas) from the external consultants that very efficiently provided their expertise.

The participating NCCs had also, thanks to the on-site format, the opportunity to interact with other NCCs facing the same challenges, and to hear from potential solutions in other countries that could be applied in their own NCC too.

For the participating CoEs, the discussed topics and concepts were further from their actual needs, so they mostly benefited to better understand the NCCs, and to learn some useful techniques that could also be applied in an adapted manner in their CoEs.

Annex 6: NCCs members of the task force "EuroCC Supercomputer Accelerator"

NCCs members of the task force "EuroCC Supercomputer Accelerator"
CYPRUS
IRELAND
ROMANIA
NORTH MACEDONIA
SWEDEN
SLOVAKIA
BELGIUM
MONTENEGRO
POLAND
FINLAND
NETHERLANDS
SERBIA
GREECE
CROATIA
TURKIYE
NORTH MACEDONIA
LATVIA
ITALY
SPAIN
SLOVENIA
FRANCE

Table 9: NCCs members of the task force "EuroCC Supercomputer Accelerator"

Annex 7: consolidated list of industry sectorial events to be commonly attended with the NCCs & interested CoEs

WP4 Partner in charge	Name	Dates	FORMAT (yearly or less)	Sector	Location	Type	NCCs that expressed interest
SCAPOS	Innovation for Health	March 2024, 28	Yearly	Life sciences and health	Rotterdam, Netherlands	Industry conference with exhibition	Netherlands, Türkiye, Croatia, Romania, Cyprus, Sweden, Latvia, Estonia, Ireland, Slovakia, Serbia, Lithuania, Luxembourg
SCAPOS	https://www.euroquic.org/ (to be discussed with NCC Finland for details)	(CASTIEL2 will discuss with NCC Finland to frame the exact opportunities)	unclear which actual meetings will be offered	Quantum computing	Unkown	(CASTIEL2 will discuss with NCC Finland to frame the exact opportunities)	Netherlands, Belgium, Türkiye, Sweden, Latvia, Estonia, Ireland, Slovakia, Spain, Serbia
TERATEC	Global Industrie Paris	March 2024, 25 -28th	Yearly	Cross-industry solutions	Paris, France	Industry trade fair	France, Croatia, Hungary, Slovakia, Lithuania
TERATEC	Viva Technology 2024	June 2024		All (including HPC and related technologies)	Paris, France	Tech trade fair	Netherlands, France, Türkiye, Hungary, Estonia, Slovakia, Spain, Serbia, Lithuania, Luxembourg
TERATEC	Forum Teratec	June 2024	Yearly	HPC and related technologies	Paris, France	HPC trade fair	Netherlands, France, Hungary, Romania, Slovakia, Spain, Serbia, Greece, Luxembourg
TERATEC	Big Data Ai Paris	September 2024	Yearly	AI and Big Data	Paris, France	AI Trade fair	France, Hungary, Romania, Cyprus, Norway, Ireland, Sweden, Slovakia, Spain

TERATEC	Paris Air Show 2025	16-22 June 2025	every 2 years	Aeronautics & Space	Paris, Le Bourget, France	International trade fair - Aeronautics & Space	Netherlands, Belgium, France, Türkiye, Sweden, Luxembourg
HLRS	Smart City Forum	May/July 2024	Yearly	transport, construction, energy, data science	Wroclaw, Poland	Industry congress	Croatia, Romania, Sweden, Latvia, Ireland, Slovakia, Lithuania
HLRS	Wind Europe Annual Event https://windeurope.org/	March 2024, 20-22	Yearly	Energy	Bilbao, Spain	Industry conference with exhibition	Netherlands, Türkiye, Norway, Sweden, Spain
HLRS	15th International Conference on Industrial use of computational fluid dynamics	June 11-13th - 2024	Irregular	Process industries and biomedical	Trondheim, Norway	Mix of Industry and Academia	Norway, Sweden, Latvia, Spain, Greece

Table 10: Consolidated list of industry sectorial events to be commonly attended with the NCCs

Annex 8: Summary of the results of the feedback questionnaire “SMEs assessment tool”

Summary of the results of the questionnaire “SMEs assessment tool”

EuroHPC
Joint Undertaking

This project has received funding from the European High-Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (JU) under grant agreement No 101102047. The JU receives support from the Digital Europe Programme and Germany, Italy, Spain, France, Belgium, Austria.

Introduction

The Task Force “SMEs assessment tool” was set up by CASTIEL2 WP4 and WP2 with the aim of upgrading HPC4SME, a tool developed by Arctur from NCC Slovenia and dedicated to the assessment of the HPC maturity of SMEs. The Task Force was led by Arctur from NCC Slovenia. The Task Force operated between March and August 2023 and it was composed by the following NCCs: Belgium, Cyprus, Estonia, Greece, Hungary, Iceland, Montenegro, Netherlands, North Macedonia, Norway, Portugal, Romania, Slovenia, Sweden and Turkey, for a total of 15 NCCs. WP2 and WP4 prepared an anonymized questionnaire dedicated to collect feedback on how the works of the Task Forces took place and on the uptake of the final product. The questionnaire was shared with Task Force members in September 2023 and 10 answers were collected. This document is a summary of the answers.

Analysis of results

Question 1: What is your overall satisfaction with this task force outcomes?
[ranking from 1 “Very dissatisfied” to 5 “Very satisfied”]

● 1
● 2
● 3
● 4
● 5

The overall satisfaction with the outcomes of the Task Force is **good**, as 8 out of 10 people were “Very Satisfied” and “Satisfied”. Two Task Force members declared that they were “Dissatisfied” with the outcome.

Question 2: Was the process used for this task force efficient in your opinion?
[ranking from 1 “Very Inefficient ” to 5 “Very efficient”]

● 1
● 2
● 3
● 4
● 5

The process undergone by the Task Force members to upgrade the SMEs assessment tool was considered “**Very Efficient**” by 7 out of 10 people. Of the remaining three answers, 1 member voted for “Efficient”, 1 for “Neutral” and 1 for “Inefficient”.

Question 3: Are you using now (or planning in the next 6 months to) the SMEs assessment tool developed in this task force for your NCC and your national ecosystem?

● YES
● NO

The uptake of the upgraded tool by the NCCs who participated in the Task Force is **very satisfactory**, as **80% of the NCCs are already using or planning to use HPC4SME in the next 6 months.**

Question 4: Do you have comments or suggestions for CASTIEL2 with regards to this tool or this task force?

The following comments were given as open answers in the questionnaire:

- For task force periodic meetings, first of all, all members should be asked about the date and time availability via doodle, framadate etc.. It is not very practical to say that we will hold the next meeting on this date and at this time.
- I think this tool will be very useful for assessment of HPC readiness and needs of SMEs. We still need to test it with SMEs in Serbia, but I think that this will be useful tool.
- Well done!
- We should shared and utilize collected data for market intelligence, competence mapping and industry steering, also (on aggregated, not individual level) for benchmark and cross-countries analyses /research.

Conclusions

Overall, the Task Force “SMEs assessment tool” is considered very successful by the Task Force members, by CASTIEL2 WP2 and WP4 and by NCC Slovenia who led the works. The way the Task Force operated was efficient and allowed to obtain a tangent result in a relatively short time. The upgraded tool will be presented to all NCCs on November 29th 2023.

Annex 9: Marketing strategy for the HPC4SME AAT, developed by NCC Slovenia

HPC4SME Automated Assessment Tool

Marketing Strategy: Guidelines

Provided by Arctur, NCC SLING Slovenia

September 2023

Introduction & Overview

The goal of this document is to provide you with some useful go-to-market (G2M) guidelines for creating an effective promotional plan for the deployment of your HPC4SME AAT. This document also includes recommendations about using promotional channels to reach potential respondents and implementing strategies to enhance user engagement among your HPC4SME AAT's target audience.

The strategy underpinning this document rests on the crucial fact that the benefits of the HPC4SME AAT are two-fold. Firstly, using an HPC4SME AAT gives you an advantage in data-driven decision-making, strategic planning, and more. Secondly, the automatically generated reports and personalized recommendations generated by the HPC4SME AAT represent a potent information resource for your HPC4SME AAT's end users, enabling them to chart their course with data-driven insights.

Ultimately, this set of guidelines will help arm you not only with the knowledge to effectively promote your HPC4SME AAT, but also with the tools to engage and excite your end users.

Unique Value Proposition of the HPC4SME AAT

We kindly invite you to visit the HPC4SME AAT website where you can start with the assessment, and find information about the European HPC landscape and funding opportunities. [Click here.](#)

When engaging potential users of your HPC4SME AAT, you may wish to reference this description. It should help you to articulate the HPC4SME AAT's unique value proposition with clarity, emphasizing its benefits, capabilities, and real-world applications.

General Steps

In this section, we outline a structured approach to effectively introduce your HPC4SME AAT to your target audience and ensure successful adoption. These steps have been designed to maximize engagement and utilization:

Pre-Release Announcement and Invitation (1-2 months prior to the official launch of your HPC4SME AAT): Announce the upcoming launch of your HPC4SME AAT around 1 to 2 months before its official release. Take this opportunity to invite potential respondents to participate in the validation phase of the tool, known as the 'closed beta'. Engage them as valuable contributors in shaping the features and capabilities, building a sense of exclusivity around their early use.

Official Launch Communication: Once your HPC4SME AAT is officially launched, clearly and impactfully communicate this fact to the target audience. When designing the Official-Launch communication, **highlight the HPC4SME AAT's availability, key features, and benefits.**

Ongoing Engagement and Education: To maintain the continuous connection, periodically reach out to potential users with updates, after the initial release. These updates can include sharing a few intriguing **results and findings that highlight your HPC4SME AAT's value.**

Repeating Assessments: Encourage respondents to repeat the assessment when required.

Marketing Channels for Reaching Potential Users

Let's explore the promotional channels that will help you reach potential users effectively. **Begin by prioritizing the promotional channels that offer the greatest reach and align with your target audience's preferences, and then gradually extend to other channels.**

Here is a set of ideas for possible promotional channels for introducing your HPC4SME AAT to potential users:

Business networks: Promote the use of your HPC4SME AAT to your Chamber of Commerce, contact various sections of your Chamber of Commerce for them to promote the use of your HPC4SME AAT to their members. Alternatively, promote the use of your HPC4SME AAT to the Enterprise Europe Network (EEN) and establish collaboration with the EEN for them to invite the SMEs to use your HPC4SME AAT as a part of the EEN's support activities. Many similar business networks exist.

Blogs: Share insights, recent success stories, and other updates. Collaborate with partners or industry influencers to amplify your reach (e.g., partner with established industry bloggers for guest posts).

News: Generate press releases or articles. These can be published on your website, through partner networks, industry news outlets, or other channels.

Newsletters: Regularly communicate with your audience through newsletters. Craft engaging newsletter content that educates and intrigues readers about your HPC4SME AAT's potential. Grab the opportunity to communicate your achievements through the EUROCC newsletter.

Event Presentations: Showcase your HPC4SME AAT at industry events, trade shows, or webinars.

1-on-1 Communication: Establish personalized communication channels and engage potential users directly by showing how your HPC4SME AAT can address their challenges effectively.

Paid Advertising: Consider paid advertising through platforms like social media or industry-specific websites.

Social Media Engagement: Leverage social media platforms to foster engagement. For example: create engaging quizzes related to your industry that subtly highlight the benefits of your HPC4SME AAT.

Podcasts and Webcasts: Collaborate with industry podcasters or host your own webcasts. Discuss industry trends and the transformative potential of your HPC4SME AAT.

Online Communities and Forums: Participate in online communities and forums relevant to your industry. Position yourself as an expert and share valuable insights about your HPC4SME AAT.

Approaches for Increasing Engagement

While the HPC4SME AAT offers substantial benefits, many potential end users might not have time to carry out the assessment (complete your online HPC4SME AAT questionnaire).

Here are some innovative strategies to motivate and engage your end users to complete the HPC4SME AAT assessment:

Vouchers: Provide end users with vouchers that they can redeem upon completing the assessment via your HPC4SME AAT.

Financing through projects: Provide end users with information about the ongoing funding and tender opportunities. The benefits of this are two-fold: firstly, the users can use the reports obtained through your HPC4SME AAT to secure funding more easily. Secondly, by sharing such valuable information you will position yourself as a go-to hub for industry actors.

Certificates: Create certificates of achievement based on the end users' score.

Badges: Similar to the certificates, a badge system can be set up to reward the users for conducting several assessments, one for each time period, tracking their individual progress. Users can proudly showcase these badges to peers.

Partnership creation: Based on the idea of issuing certificates and badges, you can establish a partnership platform for the recipients of the certificates and badges. This celebrates their achievements and builds strong ties, resulting in a community related to your HPC4SME AAT.

Surprise Rewards: Surprise users with unexpected rewards for their usage. These surprises enhance engagement and excitement.

By implementing a combination of these strategies, you can create an environment that encourages active participation and ensures that users fully experience the benefits of your HPC4SME AAT.

Conclusion

These HPC4SME AAT promotion plan guidelines aim to equip you with the practical tools and insights needed to craft an effective promotional strategy for your HPC4SME AAT.

By following these actionable steps and the approaches written below, you'll guide the HPC4SME AAT through its go-to-market journey, from pre-launch anticipation to sustained engagement and adoption.

Note: It is advisable that the specific marketing strategy tailored to your unique HPC4SME AAT be curated by the project manager, who possesses a deep understanding of both the project itself and its partners. A critical aspect of achieving a successful promotional strategy hinges on aligning the plan to the project's Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). This alignment should not only encompass the number of assessments but also extend to encompass the overarching marketing KPIs.

HPC4SME AAT uses the AAT technology developed by Arctur. If you would like to learn more about the AAT, you can find a concise yet comprehensive description of this game-changing digital tool [here](#).

Enjoy your HPC4SME AAT adventure.

Arctur team

Annex 10: Template for the industry use-cases portfolio

Concerned SECTOR*	Company logo – images-photos	
TITLE : Short Name of the use case		
<p>Company Between 140 & 170 police characters</p> <p>Challenges & Solution Between 480 & 560 police characters</p>	 Images & captions	<p style="text-align: center;">Benefits</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Between 150 & 200 characters (in bullet points)</p>
<p><i>“QUOTE from a CEO-DEVELOPER-INDUSTRY STAKHOLDER: between 280& 350 characters”</i> Name Surname, Job position/title @Company name</p>		<p>Full story: NCC Logo + QR code (incl. website to the complete story)</p>
Contact person at the NCC: Name, surname, email		

Example provided by NCC Belgium

Manufacturing & Engineering		
Understanding physics at the microscale in filter media		
<p>Company Atlas Copco is specialized in the design, development and manufacturing of industrial compressors and expanders, vacuum solutions and air and gas treatment equipment</p> <p>Challenges & Solution The flow geometry and physics at the microscale in filter media are complex and require state-of-the-art computational fluid dynamics techniques to resolve. The required computational resources are extensive and need world-class high-performance computing.</p> <p>Simulations were first performed to build the necessary experience in efficiently running large-scale calculations and exploring the computational limits. Using VSC infrastructure gave Atlas Copco access to new simulation techniques to investigate the microscale behavior of oil aerosol filter media.</p>	 Virtual filter medium microstructure Streamlines flow through a filter medium coloured by velocity magnitude	<p style="text-align: center;">Benefits</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Accelerate the development of new and better designs ✓ Simulation of more physics and larger problems that were infeasible before <p style="text-align: center;">EB: Cleaner air delivered at a lower energy cost to our customers</p>
<p><i>“Atlas Copco wanted to have a better understanding of microscale air and oil flow behaviour in oil aerosol filter media. If we better understand the physics at this scale, we can design filters with higher filtration efficiency at a lower pressure drop. This, in the end, results in cleaner air delivered at a lower energy cost to our customers”</i> Tom Saenen, Technology developer @Atlas Copco</p>		<p>Full story:</p> <div style="display: flex; align-items: center;"> </div>
Carl MENSCH, Industry EuroCC BE, carl.mensch@uantwerpen.be		

Annex 11: First industry use cases portfolio either sorted by industry sectors

Industry use-cases
EuroCC-1 & -2 portfolio
Sorted by industry sectors

Content

Industry sector	Number of use cases reported
Aeronautics	0
Agriculture	1
Automotive	0
Biotechnology/Bioinformatics	1
Chemicals	0
Cosmetics	0
Construction	0
Defence sector	0
Earth science	0
Electrical and electronic engineering	1
Energy	3
Environment/climate/weather	2
Food and drink	0
Finance/Insurance	0
Health care / Pharmaceuticals / Medical devices	4
IoT (Internet of things)	0
IT/HPC systems services & software providers	4
Life sciences	0
Manufacturing & engineering	6
Maritime	1
Material sciences	0
Mechanical engineering	1
Public services/Civil protection	2
Raw materials metals minerals and forest-based	0
Space	0
Smart City	0
Textile	0
Fashion and creative	0
Total	26

Aeronautics

0

Agriculture

1

An accurate AI-based Cloud Mask Processor for Sentinel-2

Company

KappaZeta is a remote sensing company with expertise in using radar satellite data, incorporating it with optical satellite data and providing some of the most accurate AI models on the market.

Challenges & Solution

Cloud masking is an essential step for the pre-processing of optical satellite imagery. KappaZeta addresses the problem by introducing KappaMask, an AI-based cloud and cloud shadow masking processor that uses a large convolutional segmentation model. Faster model convergence during training can be achieved by using larger batch sizes of the training data, which means more GPU memory is needed.

KappaMask was trained on an open-source dataset and fine-tuned on a Northern European terrestrial dataset which was labelled manually using the active learning methodology.

Comparison of L2A prediction output for a 512 x 512 pixels sub-tile in the test dataset.

(a) Original Sentinel-2 L2A True-Colour image; (b) KappaMask classification map.

Benefits

- ✓ Reliable cloud mask processor for Northern Europe region, which is compatible with ESA Sentinel-2 L2 processing chain
- ✓ Creation of high quality reference dataset for future developments
- ✓ Innovative application of deep learning techniques in cloud masking

Full story:

“We compared KappaMask v2 with other cloud masking processors including Sen2Cor, Fmask, MAJA, IdePix and S2Cloudless on the challenging and diverse test set. KappaMask v2 demonstrated exceptional performance reaching the highest accuracy and outperforming all the above-mentioned methods.” Tetiana Shtym, machine learning engineer @ KappaZeta

Ülar Allas, EuroCC EE, ylar.allas@ut.ee

Automotive

0

Biotechnology/Bioinformatics

1

Matchmaking, mapping industry challenges to research

Company

PUXANO is a biotech company offering structure-based protein research services to pharma and biotech companies. The company differentiates from others by developing its own technologies to accelerate the process of obtaining protein structures.

Challenges & Solution

The procondor platform helps to optimize the protein sequence in a semi-automated manner. Puxano initially used the platform internally but wanted to automate it further and make it available for others to use.

To meet this computational demand, Puxano has employed the HPC services of VSC. Furthermore, VSC introduced Puxano to the Data Science Institute of UHasselt (DSI). DSI helped Puxano design a suitable database structure. The developed database is being incorporated into the Puxano analysis pipelines and serves as the core source of information for the Puxano (web-based) service platform.

Benefits

- ✓ VSC as match-maker between Puxano and DSI
- ✓ DSI gave new insights to design a suitable database structure
- ✦ The developed database serves as the core source of information for the Puxano (web-based) service platform.

Full story:

“Our key objective was to rethink our script for protein construct design into a software platform. The idea was to find out which type of database structure served best to integrate protein information in different formats, have efficient data storage, easily updatable and searchable. Our collaboration with academia was very valuable for the success of the project” Wouter Van Putte, Director & co-Founder @Puxano

Carl MENSCH, Industry EuroCC BE, carl.mensch@uantwerpen.be

Chemicals

0

Cosmetics

0

Construction

0

Defence sector

0

Earth science

0

Electrical and electronic engineering

1

Electrical and electronic engineering

TAILSIT

Electromagnetic Simulations

Company

TAILSIT, a company from Graz, Austria produces custom-fit simulation software tools for computational electromagnetics and structural analysis.

Challenges & Solution

TAILSIT's distinctive software library employs a coupled Finite/Boundary Element Method (FEM/BEM) for electromagnetic analysis. BEM, with quadratic complexity, becomes nearly linear through Fast Multipole Method (FMM) integration. Challenges arose in limited desktop capacity. With support from the Vienna Scientific Cluster (VSC) at TU Wien the software was adapted for HPC machines, yielding significant runtime enhancements and the ability to handle problems with up to $50 \cdot 10^9$ degrees of freedom, a major leap from its previous capacity of 10^6 .

Unit cube and its calculated potential caused by a given fundamental solution

Benefits

- significant run-time improvements
- good overall scaling for up to a few thousand CPUs
- achievement of significant upscaling of degrees of freedom

Full story:

publication

Energy

3

"Based on the results and the knowledge acquired from this project, we were able to further develop our method such that the first industrial applications have been simulated. In order to harden the algorithms and thus to achieve a sustainable implementation, we will again seek cooperation with the VSC team."

Dr. Jürgen Zechner, CEO @TAILSIT

Time Series in the Energy Sector

Company

HAKOM is the technology leader for time series management in the energy industry. Its PowerTSM® Technology enables and accelerates innovation.

Challenges & Solution

The energy sector generates more data than ever before - most of it is time series data. In order to add more advanced big data analytics capabilities, the company tested its technology on a supercomputer. EuroCC Austria referred HAKOM to the experts of the Little Big Data (LBD) cluster, an HPC system at TU Wien. The successful integration of time series management (TSM) software on a highly parallel cluster enables HAKOM now to further develop the tools for analysis of very large data sets directly through its TSM system.

Benefits

- more advanced big data analytics capabilities available
- enables development of tools for analysis of very large data sets directly through its TSM system

Full story:

"With the guidance of the EuroCC team we decided to export our time series data to parquet files ... With all the data residing in the distributed network file system reading subsets of data – roughly 10 GB – into a Spark distributed data frame became both doable and reasonably fast."

Gregor Beyerle, Data Scientist @HAKOM

Contact person at the NCC: Simeon Harrison, EuroCC Austria, info@eurocc-austria.at

The Role of HPC in Ensuring Nuclear Reactor Safety

Company

Founded in Belgium 150 years ago, Tractebel is today one of the world's leading engineering companies for energy, water and infrastructure projects.

Challenges & Solution

In 2012, the federal agency of nuclear control of Belgium reported defects in the vessels of the nuclear reactor Doel 3 and Tihange 2. Among a lot of analyses, numerical simulation has been chosen to assess the risk level.

These simulations were highly computationally demanding. A single computation required a high quantity of memory (up to 128Gb for the first computations – feasibility proved up to 768Gb). Due to the high number of configurations to compute (some hundreds), combined with the memory needs, the use of HPC infrastructure was a requirement.

Benefits

- ✓ HPC helped in the assessment of structural integrity
- ✓ Safe restart of the reactors (combined with inspections)
- Tractebel acquired unique expertise and now conducts its own analyses on various parts of nuclear power plants internally but also for its partners.

Full story:

"Multiple crack configurations required much caution to perform the computation within the available hardware resources while satisfying high-quality standards in the results. Cenaero developed methodologies to face the challenges (number of configurations, memory and restitution time limitations, post-processing)." **Valéry Lacroix, Technical manager of seism & structural integrity group @Tractebel**

Contact person at the NCC: Frédérique Jacobs, Industry EuroCC BE, frederique.jacobs@cenaero.be

Computational Simulations for Emission Reduction in Combustion Plants

Company

The ORGREZ company provides services and supplies in several specific fields of power engineering, thermal engineering and ecology, generally in the processes of fuel energy conversion and electricity production and distribution.

Challenges & Solution

The main objective was to determine whether Computational Fluid Dynamics simulations could be used for the fast and efficient description of the selective catalytic reduction technology (SCR) catalysis process and, therefore, as a tool to mediate the design of a computational application for the design of this technology.

The use of numerical modelling and simulations will make the process more efficient, and faster and, most importantly, extend the application possibilities of this process, which will enable subsequent optimization of the designed solution and, thanks to high-performance computing, it will be possible to complete these simulations in a relatively short time.

CFD simulation of SCR process.

Benefits

- ✓ Confirmation of the applicability of CFD for SCR design and optimization
- ✓ Time and costs saving due to speed up of SCR design process
- ✓ Environmental impact due to optimised SCR design leading to increase of NOx emission reduction

Full story:

"By speeding up the design process of the SCR technology, time and cost savings are achieved and, in addition, the optimised SCR technology design leads to more effective NOx emission reduction and extended technology lifetime, which has a positive impact on the environment."

Vojtech Vavricka, Managing Director of the ORGREZ Division for Ecology Systems

Contact person at the NCC: Tomas Karasek, tomas.karasek@vsb.cz

Environment/climate/ weather

Sweden's Meteorology & Hydrology Institute digitizes archival tabular data using LUMI

Company

The Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute (SMHI) is an expert authority with a global perspective and a vital task of predicting changes in weather, water and climate.

Challenges & Solution

SMHI, possesses troves of archival data of observations spanning decades in paper format. The ambition of the project is to optimize and train a sufficiently accurate machine learning model which can handle different forms of tabular data, convert handwritten-text and produce machine-readable. SMHI aims to use a combination of image processing and machine learning to achieve this. The digitization pipeline is implemented in Python, using well-known open-source scientific libraries such as scikit-image and TensorFlow.

Benefits

This project aids and accelerates the digitization work from the paper archives into data, which is done manually as of now. As a result of the project, SMHI aims at digitizing numerous historical weather observations that will help a better understanding of climate, especially of the occurrence of extreme weather events.

Full story:

"A HPC allocation enables us to rapidly test and develop the product. (...) GPUs allow faster tuning hyperparameters of this model. On CPUs the neural network training takes 11 hours. On GPUs the whole training takes only 1 hour."
Ashwin Mohanan, Scientific programmer at SMHI

Contact person at the NCC: Apostolos Vasileiadis, apostolos.vasileiadis@ri.se

The multiphysics experiments of the Weather Research and Forecasting Model (WRF) on precipitation patterns of Turkey

Company

ErikTronik Engineering is a corporation that operates in several domains including aviation, energy, meteorology, and defence. They offer solutions in aviation and navigation for both military and civilian airports, design algorithms and provide energy forecasts, transform data into decision-making tools in meteorology-dependent areas, and supply spare parts to defence agencies with certifications. Additionally, ErikTronik supports projects in Turkey and the EMEA region offering consultancy, engineering, sales and after-sales services, while also addressing challenges like climate change, food, and business intelligence through engineering solutions.

Challenges & Solution

WRF model may provide accurate representation of the atmosphere and the surface conditions. However, such WRF model requires major parametrizations (e.g., cloud, planetary boundary layer, other physics options) to be optimized. On the other hand, simulations of WRF model require high computational resources to accomplish such optimization studies.

The project's sensitivity tests were completed over the Turkey domain for 2020, with a 60-combination of model physics in 4-km resolution. The combination, number, resolution, and simulation time are rather comprehensive for such sensitivity tests. We have valuable information now about which multiphysics ensemble responds favorably to the Turkey precipitation characteristics.

Previously available model performances (solid gray box on the right with a median 0.58) are improved to the level of European state of the art model accuracy levels (left gray box with median 0.66). These are very encouraging results compared with existing state of the art models.

Benefits

- ✓ Gained experience for the first time in the HPC domain.
- ✓ Encouraged to apply to the EuroHPC projects in the seasonal forecast and climate prediction areas through gained experience with this project.
- ✓ Improved their insight into driving mechanisms of precipitation over Turkey.

Full story:

"ErikTronik's enhanced forecasting in Türkiye benefits climate-dependent domains by improving resource prediction, hydrometeorological forecasting, and climate change mitigation. This capacity aids in better water management and response to climatic adversities, supporting particularly the renewable energy and agriculture sectors in risk and operational handling." **Erdem Eriğiçi, CTO @Eriktronik**

Contact person at the NCC: Sevil Sankurt, NCC Türkiye, ncc@ulakbim.gov.tr

Food and drink

0

Finance/Insurance

0

Health care / Pharmaceuticals / Medical devices

4

Health care /
Pharmaceuticals /
Medical devices

Supercomputer application in biomedical engineering

Company

AMET Ltd. is a company dedicated to development, modern manufacturing and distribution of electronic medical equipment and modules. It is a reliable and desired partner in Bulgarian and foreign market.

Challenges & Solution

The processes are substantially three-dimensional and time-dependent. The developed software tools for supercomputer simulation of coupled physical processes of radiofrequency electro surgery manipulations are beyond the scope of available commercial packages. Measurable indicators are applied to assess the reliability of the obtained results, thus providing proven criteria for minimizing subjective inaccuracies. The impact of using large-scale HPC models reached more than two times improved precision of evaluating the volume of effectively ablated tissue.

Benefits

- ✓ Fully realistic computer simulation of strongly coupled processes of radiofrequency electrosurgical technologies.
- ✓ Time/cost saving of parameter optimization of high tech low-invasive procedures.
- ✓ Assessment and optimization of hard to measure complex processes.

Full story:

"The use of state-of-the-art modeling, simulation and high performance technologies is very important to our company. The business impact from our collaboration with ICT-BAS includes improving the technology characteristics of existing products and development of new products."

Janet Popova, Managing Director @Amet Ltd.

Contact person at the NCC Bulgaria: Stanislav Harizanov, sharizanov@parallel.bas.bg

Healthcare

Medical Image Processing

Company

University Hospital Ostrava is a state-funded organisation established by the Ministry of Health of the Czech Republic. The primary purpose of this organisation is to provide health services.

Challenges & Solution

The main goal of the cooperation was to deploy and test a tool providing remote automatic tissue segmentation from patient image data obtained from computed tomography (CT) or magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) on supercomputers at IT4Innovations National Supercomputing Center.

The automated segmentation process can be applied to specific tissues of real interest to the physician, and the resulting model can be further used to plan healthcare tailored to the individual patient.

3D Slicer working environment with possible output obtained by automatic segmentation on HPC cluster.

Benefits

- ✓ The time of the segmentation process is reduced by automation
- ✓ Spared time can be used for the physician's benefit
- ✓ The automated segmentation process can be applied to specific tissues of interest to the physician

Full story:

"Using this toolkit is beneficial for both patients and physicians, as automation allows us to achieve high-quality image reconstructions in a fraction of the time and with minimal effort." **Jan Roman, MD, University Hospital Ostrava**

Contact person at the NCC: Tomas Karasek, tomas.karasek@vsb.cz

Health care /
Pharmaceuticals /
Medical devices

Topological optimization using HPC for medical devices

Company

CastPrint is a Latvian SME that provides clinics with custom-made 3D printed casts for wrist, finger, leg fractures. The casts are lighter and more breathable than the traditional gypsum fixtures.

Challenges & Solution

The Challenge

Creation of a 3D printed cast is a time-consuming and resource intensive process. Since the 3D scans used for production contain huge numbers of surface elements, processing the data on typical office computers is both slow and often unreliable, with software crashes resulting in data loss and delayed delivery to patients.

The Solution

Integrating parametric model optimization into the design process of the medical device. This involves using simulations to determine the most efficient shape for the cast, which in turn reduces the amount of material required and shortens printing times.

The use of HPC enables faster and more effective simulations, automating certain aspects of the design process and ultimately reducing the time spent on it.

Benefits

- 20% reduction in labor hours for cast design, which also reduces the risk of human error.
- Approximately 25% reduction in production material use through topological optimization.
- 25% reduction in production time through material optimization and shorter printing durations.
- Up to 15% reduction in production costs.
- Up to 25% enhanced production capacity at CastPrint.

Full story:

"There are many challenges in the production of fixators. The most important ones – how to shorten production time? how to reduce manual steps? how to save 3D printing times? These challenges also had a solution: parametric model optimization and HPC technology."

Janis Olins, CEO @CastPrint

Contact person at the NCC: Karlis Muiznieks, karlis.muiznieks@lu.lv

AI algorithm for molecule recognition

Company

Semantic Intelligence has developed an AI-driven IP Intelligence Engine enables scientists & IP experts to search, analyze and extract complex knowledge on chemical-biological interactions

Challenges & Solution

Challenge

How to index molecular images quickly & efficiently to provide users with the fastest possible access to current, published patents? The data base is one of the largest patent databases: USPTO (United States Patent and Trademark Office) with 5 million patent documents, more than 50 million molecules.

Solution

AI algorithm training in molecule recognition & integration into existing data processing workflow.

Benefits

- Successfully completed algorithm training on the database
- Confidence in the effectiveness of the HPC center infrastructure and process
- Expected time & cost saving benefits (~20-30%)

"Use of HPC allows us to perform a completely new approach to rapid analysis of big data in biopharmaceuticals, combining both structured and unstructured data to provide a data-driven, critical decision-making process to our clients."

Vita Sture, CEO @Semantic Intelligence

Full story:

Contact person at the NCC: Karlis Muiznieks, karlis.muiznieks@lu.lv

IoT (Internet of things)

IT/HPC systems, services & software providers

4

Leveraging expertise

Company

Founded in 2018, Mpacts is a SME dedicated to the development of Mpacts simulation software. It is designed to simulate the behaviour of granular materials, assemblies of large numbers of particles in industrial processes.

Challenges & Solution

While granular dynamics is conceptually very similar to molecular dynamics, it is also much more complex since particles have shape and complex interactions, which complicates contact detection. Develop computationally efficient simulation software for granular processes is critical.

The Flemish Supercomputing Center (VSC) recommended sorting the particles so that particles close in (simulated) space are also close together in computer memory. VSC also built a tool that automates the compilation of Python modules from C++/C/fortran. These programming techniques made the software more efficient and, thus, faster.

Benefits

- ✓ Sorting the particles in memory translates into faster computation times by factor 2 with existing hardware.
- ✓ Performance increases by a factor of five with GPUs
- 🔗 This improvement has a high impact on the responsiveness in solving engineering problems.

"The ability to work with the highly skilled experts in the field of HPC at VSC was a very interesting and rewarding experience. I would recommend anyone involved in supercomputing to contact the VSC and benefit from their available expertise to improve your calculations." **Simon Vanmaercke, Co-Founder @Mpacts**

@Mpacts

Full story:

Carl MENSCH, Industry EuroCC BE, carl.mensch@uantwerpen.be

IT/HPC systems,
services & software
providers

machinetutors

Large Scale Real-Time Image Content Moderation

Company

Founded in 2010, Machinetutors provides machine learning consultancy and customized AI software development services. Machinetutors empowers businesses all over the world by solving real-world problems.

Challenges & Solution

This project addresses the problem of large-scale real-time image-based content moderation. The system is deployed to a production environment where tens of thousands of users browse the internet daily. The system must be both accurate and run in real-time to meet the business requirements. Moreover, the model size must be small so that multiple copies of the model can be run simultaneously on a GPU to reduce server costs. A major challenge has been making several models work efficiently together.

In order to solve the problem defined, we develop three main models. In the first model, we propose a multi-label NSFW classifier that can detect the NSFW levels (light, medium, hard) and predict other labels, such as the real person and clothing characteristics. The second model is a one-stage body-based age & gender detection model. Current age & gender methods are both face based i.e. they use face bounding boxes and are two-stage processes, they first run a face detector and then run the model on these boxes. When multiple faces are present in an image, this approach fails to meet the real-time requirement. The third one is a segmentation model. These three models run in a pipeline via which we can run various scenarios.

Benefits

- ✓ Run many experiments in parallel
- ✓ Run larger batch size trainings on newer GPUs
- ✓ Access many GPUs for hyperparameter tuning
- ✓ Gain a considerable competitive advantage in the global AI ecosystem considering the speed and the cost-efficiency

Full story:

"EuroCC project made it possible for our company to play a major role in the transformation of a content safety technology start-up into a leading organization in Europe. The state of the art artificial intelligence models our team trained would not have been achievable without the computation resources they provided." Eray Berger, CEO @Machinetutors

Contact person at the NCC: Sevil Sankurt, NCC Türkiye, ncc@ulakbim.gov.tr

IoT, IT/HPC
systems, services
& software

ERSTE

EURO²

Fine-tuning speech-to-text models on HPC clusters

Company

Erste Software (2017), located in Türkiye, is an SME focused on IoT, mobile device management, and using ML/AI techniques in practice.

Challenges & Solution

The sales/quotation preparation process in manufacturing is a tedious task with back-and-forth messages in between the customer and manufacturer, since production requires high-precision under strict time-to-deliver constraints. A major part of the process is daily meetings between the engineering and sales teams. Recording this crucial know-how, transcribe it to enable semantic search for the current and future quotations is important. To address this problem, Erste's decision was to fine-tune a pre-trained model, Whisper, for Turkish. Yet an accurate fine-tuning requires significant computational power. Although Erste had experience in traditional ML training, they lack access and expertise on using multiple GPUs for this purpose. In this use-case, they leverage the expertise in the NCC Türkiye and computational resources to fine-tune a large-scale model.

Benefits

- ✓ Gained experience in utilizing TRUBA HPC resources and training large-scale models with large-scale datasets.
- ✓ Enhance the efficiency and quality of customer's manufacturing endeavours in the long run.
- ✓ Significantly improved the accuracy of Whisper, a speech-to-text model for Turkish.

Full story:

"Thanks to this opportunity, Erste Software had a rewarding experience on working with academicians and HPC experts in the EuroCC team. In addition to increasing the accuracy and cost-efficiency of our solution, for our future projects, we gained valuable experience on using HPC resources and working with large-scale datasets and models." Özer Aydemir, Co-founder and CEO @Erste

Contact person at the NCC: Sevil Sankurt, NCC Türkiye, ncc@ulakbim.gov.tr

IoT, IT/HPC
systems, services
& software

VLMedia

EURO²

AI-Driven Style Transfer for Virtual Environments

Company

Founded in 2014, VL Media is a software company focussed on designing and creating user-friendly social apps and games.

Challenges & Solution

One of the projects carried out by the company is to customize the scene in the virtual environment and the audio-visual objects within the scene by the content producers. In order to make more original designs, different studies, and experiments will be carried out using the style transfer of these images determined by the content producer by using artificial intelligence. Style transfer is frequently used today thanks to the advancement of GPU technology. Since all the methods used by the company to realize such designs require GPU processing power.

The customized multi-GPU strategy adopted in the project is favoured for its alignment with the model's characteristics and workload requirements. DataParallel serves the purpose of providing more general and straightforward multi-GPU support, combining multi-GPU processing and multi-scale production to achieve high-quality, high-resolution results.

Benefits

- ✓ Enhanced Customization in Virtual Environments
- ✓ Hybrid Style Transfer Technique
- ✓ Balanced Content and Style Preservation
- ✓ Customized Multi-GPU Strategy

Full story:

"I'm thrilled to collaborate with TRUBA's experts in the realm of style transfer. Together, the fusion of our creative ideas and high-performance computing, in the exciting domain of style transfer, is crafting a new visual language that will redefine what's possible."

Eda Yüksel, CRO @VLMedia

Contact person at the NCC: Sevil Sankurt, NCC Türkiye, ncc@ulakbim.gov.tr

Life sciences

EURO²

Manufacturing & engineering

6

Manufacturing & Engineering

Understanding physics at the microscale in filter media

Company

Atlas Copco is specialized in the design, development and manufacturing of industrial compressors and expanders, vacuum solutions and air and gas treatment equipment.

Challenges & Solution

The flow geometry and physics at the microscale in filter media are complex and require state-of-the-art computational fluid dynamics techniques to resolve. The required computational resources are extensive and need world-class high-performance computing.

Simulations were first performed to build the necessary experience in efficiently running large-scale calculations and exploring the computational limits. Using VSC infrastructure gave Atlas Copco access to new simulation techniques to investigate the microscale behavior of oil aerosol filter media.

Benefits

- ✓ Accelerate the development of new and better designs
- ✓ Simulation of more physics and larger problems that were infeasible before
- ✦ **Cleaner air delivered at a lower energy cost to our customers**

Full story:

"Atlas Copco wanted to have a better understanding of microscale air and oil flow behaviour in oil aerosol filter media. If we better understand the physics at this scale, we can design filters with higher filtration efficiency at a lower pressure drop. This, in the end, results in cleaner air delivered at a lower energy cost to our customers" **Tom Saenen, Technology developer @Atlas Copco**

Carl MENSCH, Industry EuroCC BE, carl.mensch@uantwerpen.be

Manufacturing & Engineering

PLYGEAR

Manufacturing & engineering

Mikrotvornica

Improving the furniture precision

Company

PLYGear is specialized in the design, computer modelling and manufacturing of furniture born in timely recorded digital dreams supported by the plywood unique properties.

Challenges & Solution

The models designed and implemented in virtual environment are complex and require state-of-the-art computational techniques to resolve. The required computational resources are extensive and need high-performance computing as all PLYgear items need the precision of the modern processing methods.

Simulations were performed to acquire knowledge in running effectively new design methods. The impact of using large-scale HPC models improved both the precision and the production rate.

Benefits

- Accelerate the development of new designs via simulations
- Each model is designed and implemented in virtual environment
- ✦ **a functional minimalist design offered to our customers**

Full story:

"PLYGear wanted to have a better approach to furniture design for a complex environment by mixing ideas with passion and engineering precision. The most characteristic of all PLYGear items is that thanks to the precision of the modern processing methods the assemblies are made extremely reliable and impeccable." **Borislav Georgiev, MS in Engineering, Technology Developer @PLYGear**

Contact person at the NCC BG: Ana Proykova, anap@phys.uni-sofia.bg

HPC-based Stabilization for Additive Manufacturing

Company

Mikrotvornica d.o.o. specializes in high-quality prototype and product production using advanced technologies, with a strong focus on additive and digital manufacturing.

Challenges & Solution

The aim of the project is to reduce heat-induced deformations in 3D-printed objects. These deformations can significantly affect the quality and functionality of the final product. Based on computational fluid dynamics simulations performed using the HPC infrastructure, through an iterative processes and fine-tuning, an improved 3D printer assembly was created. In addition, the additive manufacturing process was improved by outlining and providing complete control over the parameters that affect the dimensional stability of 3D printed products.

Benefits

- ✓ Shorter delivery times by up to 50%.
- ✓ Reduction of up to 30% in production costs.
- ✓ Savings of €150.000,00 over a period of three years.
- ✓ Increase in sales by up to 30%.

Full story:

"In cooperation with the members of NCC Croatia (RBI), we were provided with professional support and extensive experience with regards to the application of high-performance computing in order to improve 3D printing characteristics and capacities." **Nikola Blažević, CEO @Mikrotvornica**

Lado Kranjčević, NCC Croatia, lado.kranjcevic@riteh.hr

Digital Twin Framework for Hydrofoil Optimization

Company

Marotti Windsurfing d.o.o. is a company founded by the two-time windsurfing champion. MWSC is dedicated to the development and production of windsurfing equipment.

Challenges & Solution

In close cooperation with IIT d.o.o., specialized equipment and software were developed to ensure precise measurements of fluid data. A methodology based on reverse engineering and digital twin technology was developed to design an optimized hydrofoil. The mold creation process saw collaboration with members from the Academia and Bex d.o.o., resulting in a robust approach to aluminium mould production. State-of-the-art techniques were employed to produce and thoroughly test new hydrofoil prototypes.

Hydrofoil mold used to create a prototype design.

Benefits

- ✓ Enhanced hydrofoil windsurfing performance.
- ✓ Competitive and industrial advantage (improved products).
- ✓ Industry/company growth.
- ✓ International recognition.
- ✓ Futureproofing.

Full story:

"I am grateful for the accessibility, willingness, and enthusiasm in order to jointly achieve success. Our goal is to create a so-called 'speed foil' hydrofoil with which we will attempt to break the speed world record. I am confident, based on current results, that we will achieve this."
Enrico Marotti, CEO @Marotti Windsurfing

Contact person at the NCC: Lado Kranjčević, NCC Croatia, lado.kranjcevic@riteh.hr

Use of Bulk Simulation in the Development of a Rail Freight Wagon

Company

Advanced Engineering is a company that focuses on computer simulations, structural analysis and optimisation of structures, and multi-physics modelling and simulation.

Challenges & Solution

End customers and users asked for a guarantee for the time required to unload each wagon during unloading, and the development team needed to make sure that the geometry of the hoppers and funnels would ensure the complete discharge of bulk material without it being stuck to the walls.

The solution can simulate the interaction of the bulk material with the structure, the ability to compare multiple design options, and the ease of analysing the behaviour of different grain types under various external conditions such as temperature and humidity.

Ongoing simulation of emptying a freight wagon box – one-quarter simulation model.

Benefits

- ✓ Time and costs savings through numerical modelling and simulations
- ✓ The ability to simulate the interaction of the bulk material with the structure
- ✓ The ability to compare multiple design options

Full story:

"The advantage of computer simulations of bulk material movement for this problem over physical testing is that the cost of hiring grain silos and grain costs are eliminated." **Tomas Curda, Business Development Manager, Advanced Engineering, s.r.o.**

Contact person at the NCC: Tomas Karasek, tomas.karasek@vsb.cz

Nilar automates battery inspection using AI vision on Vega

Company

Nilar AB develops and manufactures batteries that are safe and re-usable, which is crucial for a climate transition that works, i.e. that electricity is actually there when it is needed and not just when it is generated.

Challenges & Solution

Quality inspection is an essential part of the battery manufacturing process, since quality determines battery performance, lifespan, and safety. Inspection should ideally be done for every part of every battery, but the high production rate makes this very difficult to achieve without automation. ENCCS and Nilar AB have leveraged the computational resources that the EuroHPC JU Vega cluster provides and the large image datasets Nilar has collected from their assembly lines to develop an AI-based computer vision solution as a first step towards complete automation of Nilar's quality inspection process.

Benefits

- Spot negative trends earlier
- Faster manufacturing adjustment
- Reduce scrap rate

Full story:

"From the supercomputing access, Nilar is already seeing benefits from the solution, such as being able to spot negative trends in quality earlier, which enables faster adjustment of process parameters to reverse these trends. This has helped reduce scrap rate, which in turn has led to a positive impact on their business."

Andreas Thore, Researcher at ENCCS/RISE

Contact person at the NCC: Apostolos Vasileiadis, apostolos.vasileiadis@ri.se

Maritime

The 1st Big Data solution applied to maritime industries

Company

Young start-up located in Normandy

Sinay allows you to exploit your data and provides you with key indicators to manage your activity.

Challenges & Solution

At the end of 2017, SINAY made a first visit to CRIANN and joined the SIMSEO program. SINAY engineers benefited from a training session and a personalized support to implement the codes on the computer and to use resources optimally. The acceleration of performance was obtained by the development of a parallel version of the code, which coupled with the use of a calculator, leads to a notable reduction in calculation time for modelling.

- Benefits**
- ✓ Noticeable reduction in calculation time: from several years to a few hours.
 - ✓ Ability to model large geographic areas.
 - ✓ Accelerated development of the SINAY Acoustics application.

Full story:

"SINAY is very satisfied with the support within the EUROCC program both technically and financially. We have gained considerably in productivity for the development of our solution Acoustics."

Yanis SOUAMI, CEO SINAY

Marie-Sophie CABOT, Industry Euro CC FR, Marie-Sophie.Cabot@criann.fr

Material sciences

0

Mechanical engineering

1

Dynamic Fluid-Object Interactions During Motion

Company

AITAC d.o.o. is a local subsidiary providing yacht, naval, cruise ship, marine & offshore engineering and PLM services in shipbuilding and offshore industry.

Challenges & Solution

Simulating the movement of submerged objects in a fluid-filled tank can be a challenging task. The dynamic interaction introduces a variety of problems e.g. sloshing and potential spillage, all of which must be accurately characterized and effectively mitigated. The use of high performance computing is indispensable for the successful execution of these computational fluid dynamics simulations.

A carefully crafted plan for the optimal motion of objects is proposed. This plan represents a delicate equilibrium between the minimization of waiting times and the prevention of water spillage, and as such improves the overall system performance.

- Benefits**
- ✓ Optimized system performance by minimizing waiting times
 - ✓ Facilitated the rapid exploration of novel design possibilities
 - ✓ Optimal movement plan contributes to safer and more reliable system

Full story:

"We were interested in the displacement of the water during the movement and were unsure of the bottom's impact on the flow and the force due to the negative pressure. Given that this is a component of a larger system, we needed a solution that would ensure uninterrupted and optimal operation."

Domagoj Borucinsky, Engineer @AITAC

Lado Kranjčević, NCC Croatia, lado.kranjcevic@riteh.hr

Public services/Civil protection

2

Security

Tool to fight criminality more effectively

Company

The Police of the Czech Republic are an armed security force established by the National Council Act of 21 June 1991. The Police of the Czech Republic serves the public.

Challenges & Solution

The practical part of the Maps of the Future II project aimed to use crime data to develop and test new procedures and tools for more effective crime fighting and more targeted, efficient, and thus cheaper use of resources (personnel, financial, and material).

Models designed to predict crime and socio-pathogenic phenomena throughout the Czech Republic were successfully developed and tested. The possibility of running memory and computationally demanding tasks in parallel using dedicated graphics cards proved crucial, allowing individual experiments to be reduced from days to hours.

Photo provided by the Police of the Czech Republic.

Benefits

- ✓ The criminality prediction model training time was reduced several fold
- ✓ The training done on the GPU nodes of the Karolina cluster was shown to be effective
- ✓ The solution will help the Police of the Czech Republic increase the efficiency of their patrol planning.

Full story:

"I am very pleased that the employees of the Police of the Czech Republic are actively involved in the search for innovations and solutions to one of the current topics in the internal security of the Czech Republic, which is the effective use of available resources (both human and material)." **genmjr. Martin Vondrasek, Police President**

Contact person at the NCC: Tomas Karasek, tomas.karasek@vsb.cz

Public services/ Civil protection

SLB·analysis Analyse Air Pollution Flow Using MeluXina Supercomputer

Company

Stockholms luft- och bulleranalys (SLB·analysis) is a unit at the Environment and Health Administration of the City of Stockholm. The unit is responsible for monitoring outdoor air quality in the city.

Challenges & Solution

The dispersion of aerosol particles in urban environments heavily depends on meteorological parameters, in particular air flows. SLB·analysis run scaling tests on EuroHPC JU resources to push the boundaries of CFD simulations using OpenFOAM to larger spatial domains and higher complexity.

Benefits

- Simulating larger urban area becomes possible
- Time-to-solution is greatly reduced
- Better results used for air quality assessment

"By using more complex turbulence models, the accuracy of the results will be improved so that there can be an investigation whether new developments will meet air quality limits and propose measures to improve air quality in sensitive areas."

Qiang Li, Research software engineer, ENCCS

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Raw materials, metals, minerals and forest-based

0

Space

0

Smart City

0

Textile

0

Fashion and creative

0

EuroCC: Use cases portfolio

coordinated by CASTIEL2-WP4

EuroHPC
Joint Undertaking

This project has received funding from the European High-Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (JU) under grant agreement No 951732. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and Germany, Bulgaria, Austria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Latvia, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, United Kingdom, France, Netherlands, Belgium, Luxembourg, Slovakia, Norway, Switzerland, Turkey, Republic of North Macedonia, Iceland, Montenegro

Annex 12: Results of the NCCs TPRs for Q1 and Q2

The results for the first two quarters (Q1: January-March 2023 and Q2: April-June 2023) were collected by the PMT and forwarded to CASTIEL2-WP4. CASTIEL2-WP4 processed these figures, the results are:

Regarding the PoCs:

- As phase 2 was only re-starting, the Figure 12 shows that the NCCs declare a number of PoCs finalised with SMEs are between 0 (or no answer for the moment) and 6.

Figure 12: Number of PoCs finalised with SMEs.
(Q1 + Q2 figures, January 2023 - June 2023)

- At the end of June 2023, only two countries had done PoCs with Big industry stakeholders.

Regarding the initiated projects:

- Figure 13 shows that 19 NCCs declared between 1 and 5 projects initiated with SMEs and 4 NCCs declared between 6 and 20 projects initiated with SMEs, by end of June 2023.

Figure 13: Numbers of projects initiated with SMEs
(Q1 + Q2 figures, January 2023 - June 2023)

- The Figure 14 shows that 3 NCCs declared 1 project initiated with Big Industry, 2 NCCs declared 2 projects initiated with Big Industry and 2 NCC declared 5 projects initiated with SMEs, by end of June 2023.

Figure 14: Numbers of projects initiated with Big Industry (Q1 + Q2 figures, January 2023 - June 2023)

Regarding the finalised projects:

- As phase 2 was only re-starting, the Figure 15 shows that 8 NCCs declared between 1 and 5 projects finalised with SMEs and 1 NCC indicated between 6 and 20 projects finalised with SMEs, by end of June 2023.

Figure 15: Numbers of projects finalised with SMEs. (Q1 + Q2 figures, January 2023 - June 2023)

- At the end of June 2023, only three countries declared that they had 1 project finalised with Big industry stakeholders.

Annex 13: FAQ Industry figures for the TPRs

FAQ: How to fill in the quarterly TPR tables about industry interactions?

1. **What is a “PoC”?** PoC means “Proof-of-concept”.
2. **What can be considered as a “project”?**

In the industry tables, a project is every initiative **with concrete outcomes** for your industry stakeholder that is **not** a PoC (as the PoCs are already declared in the first line “number of PoCs done”), and on which you could provide/**showcase some clear material evidence** (success stories, official news or announcement, collaboration agreement, MoU, etc.). The following can be counted as projects:

- Technical support or consultancy (i.e. technical expertise or financial advice or help for writing a proposal, etc) provided to a company for them to submit a proposal to a funding agency or funding from another project (ex: FF4EuroHPC, other calls)
- Technical support or consultancy (i.e. technical expertise or financial advice or help for writing an application, etc) provided to a company for them to access to a JU supercomputer
- Technical support or consultancy (i.e. technical expertise or financial advice or help for writing an application or request, etc) provided to a company for them to get computation hours on a national machine
- collaboration agreement/MoU signed
- after interaction with the company, support provided to put them in contact with your local EDIH, chamber of commerce, technology transfer institution, with a relevant research centre, etc.
- etc

IN CASE YOU HAVE POTENTIAL DOUBTS OR SUGGESTIONS FOR OTHER types of “projects” to be counted, please contact *[WP4 contact email]* to enrich this list of examples.

3. **If a project started in EuroCC2, but then was moved to another project and actually finalised within that other project, is it eligible to be counted/declared in the quarterly TPR?**

Yes, all projects that benefited from resources (personnel or other direct costs) from EUROCC2 at some point (i.e. to initialize it, or to finalize it), and that was initiated **during the quarter of this TPR (i.e. the last 3 months)** should be declared in the current TPR. In this case, the project should be counted in the line “Projects initiated”.

4. **Is a project that started in EuroCC1 and finalised during EuroCC2 eligible to be counted in the appropriate TPR of EuroCC2?**

Yes, all projects that benefited from resources (personnel or other direct costs) from EUROCC2 at some point (i.e. to initialise it, or to finalise it), and that finalised **during the last quarter (i.e. the last 3 months)** should be declared in the current TPR. In this case, the projects should be counted in the line “Projects finalised”.

DIGITAL-EUROHPC-JU-2022-NCC-01

Centres of Excellence (CoEs) Industry topics

July 2023

Information collected by WP4 of CASTIEL (Industrial Interaction and Business Development) in interaction with the industry champions of the CoEs

**Coordination & Support
for National Competence Centres on a European Level Phase 2
Project Number: 101102047**

EuroHPC
Joint Undertaking

This project has received funding from the European High-Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (JU) under grant agreement No 101102047. The JU receives support from the Digital Europe Programme and Germany, Italy, Spain, France, Belgium, Austria.

List of abbreviations

CASTIEL2	Phase 2 of CASTIEL
CoE	Centre of Excellence
EuroCC2	Phase 2 of EuroCC
EuroHPC JU	The European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking
HPC	High-Performance Computing
JU	Short version of EuroHPC Joint Undertaking
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
NCC	National Competence Centre
PMT	Project Management Team
PoC	Proof of Concept
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
WP	Work Package

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1 Introduction

WP4 of CASTIEL organized concept-board discussions with the NCCs and the CoEs during the “CoEs kick-off meeting” organized by CASTIEL-WP2 in April 2023. During this meeting, through the various talks of the CoEs and thanks to the concept-board completed by the NCCs and CoEs representatives, initial information regarding the interaction with industry of the CoE was collected. This information was completed at the specific first meeting of WP4-CoEs industry champions in July 2023 (3 iterations of this first meeting happened in July 2023) and via emails.

The objective was to gather the key aspects (goals, challenges, material or resources available, etc.) of the CoEs when it comes to industry, in order to share this information with the other CoEs, the NCCs (and later on with the JU and the reviewers) and to allow and foster collaborations, exchange of knowledge and better visibility within the EuroCC2, the CoEs and CASTIEL2 projects. The information collected between April 2023 and July 2023 and presented in this document will be updated regularly (at least yearly) thanks to the regular discussions that will take place with the CoEs.

2 Objectives regarding Industry outreach and provision of services

There are two types of CoEs: Type 1 (preparing applications in the Exascale era) and Type 2 (for supporting supercomputing applications for Science and Innovation).

- Four CoEs are Type 1: MaX, SPACE, Plasma-PEPSC and CEEC (HORIZON-EUROHPC-JU-2021-COE-01-01)
- Six CoEs are Type 2: ChEESE-2P, BioExcel-3, EXCELLERAT P2, ESiWACE3, HiDALGO2 and MultiXscale (HORIZON-EUROHPC-JU-2021-COE-01-02).

The CoEs-Type 2 generally have interest or clear goals to interact with industry, whereas the CoEs-Type 1 are more academic-oriented, with still unclear or not at all interest to interact with industry.

The following Table 1 summarizes the importance of the industry topics for the CoEs:

Table 1: Industrial outreach & provision of services (& Services portal)

CoE	COE-TYPE	Industrial Outreach	Provision of services	Existing services Portal
EXCELLERAT-2	Type 2	Yes (& associated partners)	Yes (specific WP for that)	https://services.excellerat.eu/
CEEC	Type 1	Not really: only light interest, as no industry outreach plans in the GA (but would say ok if contacted for specific interaction)	NO - essentially academic targets	-
HiDALGO2	Type 2	Yes : primarily for environmental solutions (concerning industry),or with industry intermediaries, and also with governmental organizations.	Yes: Provision of solution access to SMEs. 4 families of applications and 2 are directly targeting industry, there are also potential for industry wrt their applications, or the general used techniques	-
ChEES2	Type 2	Unclear but industry and users board that includes Oil & Gas companies, also insurance BUT mostly focused on public institutions (>40 industry companies in the board at end of Cheese1) 2 different levels of interactions: i) Small group of institutions/industries with whom they regularly interact for further definition of exploitation pathways, ii) Large group of institutions, associations, etc. which are regularly informed about the project progress	YES: Mainly focused on public sector.	None (could be refined in the future)
MaX3	Type 1	Not really, since as track 1 CoE but "Door open for collaboration"	In some way: Max3 did offer a set of services for expert users from industry.	http://www.max-centre.eu/services
SPACE	Type 1	NO	NO	-
MultiXScale	Type 2	In some way: Have collaboration with IT companies but no budget for PoC studies	In some way: Training yes, o.w. not directly. Cloud providers are providing apps sw as services to their users (customers)	-
Plasma-PEPSC	Type 1	NO (only starting, this could be refined in the future). They have 2 industry partners, so this might change later on.	NO (only starting, this could be refined in the future)	None (could be refined in the future)
BioExcel-3	Type 2	Yes	Yes but in a limited way, and details to be discussed case-by-case	https://bioexcel.eu/services/
ESiWACE-3	Type 2	Indirectly: Meteo organisations & Climate modelling generate results (& the DestinationEarth Digital Twin) that indirectly provide value for various industries.	Maybe very indirectly by Meto Centres / DestinE)	https://www.esiwace.eu/services

3 Main goal, structure and presentation of the processes to outreach industry

The CoEs are structured in different ways, therefore their interaction with industry can take several shapes.

A summary of their structure, their vision of industry outreach and their interest (or obligation according to this DoA) for outreach of external industry stakeholders is gathered in the Table 2 below. (Caption of the coloured background for the column INDUSTRY OUTREACH: The CoEs open to collaboration with industry or with active industry outreach have a background in green, the others in yellow).

Table 2: Goal, structure and interest to target outreach to external industry stakeholders

CoE	Complete name/topic	Goal	Structure	INDUSTRY OUTREACH	Does your CoE (& your DoA) target outreach to industrial organisations not involved in the consortium and if so, would you look to provide (commercial) services to them?
EXCELLERAT-2	<i>CoE for supporting supercomputing engineering applications from large scaling to the exascale</i>	<i>to enable the use of simulations workflow at a large scale to exascale computing challenges</i>	7 WPs: -1 PM -3 technical WPs -3 outcome WPs: WP5 center implementation, WP6 Market context & business development, WP7 Awareness, impact creation & outreach	- via interest groups, dedicated "community building" task in WP7. - via WP6 and WP7 to provide sales/marketing-orientated messages from the services and product owners and dissemination material - development of services and product offering on the EXCELLERAT SERVICE PORTAL from the technical WPs - Improvement of the TRL from the services and products of the technical partners to be able to offer them on the market	At the moment, the EXCELLERAT CoE does not offer its services and products directly on a marketplace, but rather a catalogue of services and products offered by the consortium's technical partners, and no doubt in the future by external non-commercial and commercial vendors. These services and products are invoiced directly by their owners, e.g. training, workshops, and consultancy for institutions that have the right to invoice. As far as code/software is concerned, it has to reach TRL 9 levels before it can be offered on the market en masse. Generally speaking, in order for CoE EXCELLERAT to be able to invoice services and products directly after funding, they must have the highest TRL level in order to be able to offer them on the market en masse, adapt the marketing/sales solutions according to the final services and products and develop these commercial channels according to the resources available.

ChEESE2	<i>Center of Excellence (CoE) in the domain of Solid Earth</i>	<i>Identification of exascale computational challenges in geophysics (natural hazards) in term of capability computing, capacity computing, urgent computing</i>	<p>3 pillars: 1) scientific community 2) EuroHPC infrastructures & NCCs 3) public & private industry parties benefiting from the products & downstream services on geohazards</p> <p>11 open-source flagships codes 15 simulation cases For the 3rd pillar (public & private parties): co-design with mini-apps with EPI, EUPEX and EuPilot initiative. Some TRL 8 or 9, that went into operations.</p>	<p>Service enabling (rather targeting EU institutions or academic purposes ...): 2 categories -> urgent computing service enabling at EuroHPC systems (emergency access mode) -> services integrated in EPOS thematic core services</p> <p>Outreach & community building: Industry and Users board (2 levels): Full IUB members, IUB members): large companies, public bodies, associations, to test & validate pilots: 14 validation cases & 6 live exercises. Co-design with end-users is 1 of the 3 pillars.</p>	<p>This CoE does not provide services with a high TRL since they are focusing on the public sector, yet they have a few collaborations with some industrial gas companies for geo-resources and exploration.</p> <p>They would be interested in collaborations with the NCCs, depending on the countries (potential in their field)</p>
CEEC	<i>Centre of Excellence in Exascale CFD</i>	<i>Adress the extreme-scale computing challenge to enable the use of CFD simulations at exascale.</i>	Use of machine like LUMI Lighthouse cases & codes are focused on aeronautics or wind-turbines	Interested in outreach for industry but not the priority due to previous experiences for this high-level use cases, and no industry outreach plans in the GA	The CoE is more focused on academia for outreach, previous experiences with industry have shown that most of them are reluctant to collaborate with the CoE due to the simulations' prices. So, the priority n°1 is academia.
HiDALGO2	<i>Centre of Excellence in Urban-migration simulation topics</i>	<i>bring together advanced solutions (HPC HPDA AI) to provide stakeholders & decision makers tools that would mitigate tragic consequences of climate & civilization phenomenon by delivering necessary knowledge</i>	<p>The objectives are distributed in Conceptual services: 4 areas: technological, multidisciplinary, socio-scientific, team working objectives. 4 current use cases: urban air project (TRL6), urban buildings (), renewable energy sources, wildfires. Project components (see the slides). Main topics of interest for phase 2: Exascale support for Global Challenges, DATA EXPLoration and visualisation</p>	So far, have initiated cooperation with one large company (UAP pilot) and several (4) local governments. 0 cooperation with SMEs and count on NCCs that have better contacts and insight in this regard	The CoE is interested in interacting with both Big Industry (phase 1 saw provision of services for group corporations with some requirements and expectation of specific results) and SMEs (potential so focus would be the portal for submitting requests for simulation/visualisation, could also provide customisation of existing simulations for new cities/areas)

MaX3	<i>MAX designs new materials at the exascale</i>	<i>Turn MaX lighthouse codes into exascale-enabled applications Enabling materials for grand challenges</i>	7 WPs: -1 MGT -4 technical WPs -WP5 training & community engagement, WP6 communication, exploitation & dissemination	Services / industry outreach: they don't have a specific task for services or industry. However, they collected a catalogue of services, including available for industry. Limits there would be time and people available Trainings aiming at academia & industry	This CoE is not focused on industry interactions since they are a track 1 CoE. However they would be open to collaborations if raised with industry and/or NCCs
SPACE	<i>Scalable Parallel Astrophysical Code for Exascale Center of Excellence (CoE) for HPC astrophysical applications</i>	<i>outstanding quality & volume of data => exceptional challenges to their theoretical interpretation. 8 codes in 3 main themes 5 objectives: to evolve the 8 codes, evolve data analysis & visualization ecosystem, dvp ML techniques, address the energy efficiency issue, federate the A&C community</i>	3 private companies in the consortium WP1: mgt WP2/3: science (interaction in WP2 with HW providers) WP4: tools (transversal for the others) WP5: dissemination, outreach, training for the A&C community	<i>UNKNOWN</i>	The astrophysics research field doesn't particularly allow for industry outreach due to its specificity but the CoE is open to contacts and collaborations since their developments can be useful to everyone. The CoEs are not focused only on SMEs except for two exceptions, so a reflection on how the technologies of the CoEs could flow towards the SMEs via the NCCs is needed by CASTIEL2.
MultiXScale	<i>Performance, portability, productivity</i>	<i>Application co-design for exascale, accelerate development, deploy scientific workflows... interest in co-design Objective: increase performance, productivity and portability for scientists & pilot multiscale use-cases of societal and industrial significance.</i>	Collaboration with the CERN Best practices: git repositories, merge requests etc.. Work on EESSI -> huge interest from the audience a priori	Interaction with industry users (to test) We offer services, training, Ambassador's programme within the CoE Already collaboration with industry, plan to expand it. Very low budget, some efforts for industry (9PM).	The CoE is considering commercial services such as trainings for software and applications and services for distribution.

Plasma-PEPSC	<i>Plasma exascale performance simulations CoE</i>	<i>Fusion energy research and modern industries depends on plasma science and technology, plasma simulations for societal challenges, HPC, supercomputers and virtual prototyping have an important role in predicting observations and in design => pushing flagship plasma simulation codes to tackle exascale enabled grand challenges.</i>	3 technical WPs (2.3.4.5) with use cases; WP6: dissemination, community building, training and exploitation . WP1 drives the project (on tech viewpoint) WP7 on admin management Methods: performance optimization and co-design	Co-design with EuroHPC Systems with LUMI & supercomputers + with EPI processor & accelerator (that include industry like SIPEARL: part of the consortium) codes -> challenges -> Exascale systems, data analytics... -> Programming models and algorithms -> software, data, roadmap, publication, skills, collaborations towards impact	The CoE plans to provide services in the far future, not right now
BioExcel-3	<i>Center of excellence for Computational Biomolecular Research</i>	<i>Supports computational molecular life sciences (neurosciences, drug discovery etc.) and developing exascale for life science. Provide researchers with high-quality user-friendly software, to increase their expertise and skills. Codes world leading open-source software like GROMACS, HADDOCK...</i>	3rd phase of the CoE Methods: use Mare Nostrum	Use of collaboration multipliers through users & key professionals. Interaction with some industry users through their codes. Training programme, with schools and remote training framework Offers services: training and support for long-term career development. offers official support resources: forums, webinars, documentation and events. Collaboration with Astra Zeneca, Janssen, Royal Society of Chemistry Ambassador Program: preliminary engagement with Bulgaria, Cyprus, Greece, Italy, Lithuania, Slovenia and Türkiye.	the previous phase of the CoE already included industry outreach as an objective and will continue during this new phase

<p>ESiWACE-3</p>	<p><i>Excellence in simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe</i></p>	<p><i>Focus on supporting the modelling community to reach a higher TRL for exascale supercomputing and foster knowledge transfer in EU.</i></p> <p><i>Objective: evolution: enable leading EU weather and climate models to leverage performance of pre-exascale systems, revolution: make use of exascale.</i></p>	<p>3 pillars: scalability of codes and of software development, usability of workflows in HPC environment and exploitability of data. Pillar 2 includes community building wrt earth system modelling Pillar 1: WP1,2,3,about tech developmt. Pillar 2: WP4,5,6 about services and networking with community. WP5-> training & capacity building Partners, includes industry company Atos! Core services -> infrastructures -> R&I -> Community engagement</p>	<p>Offers training events, summer schools and hackathons</p>	<p>The CoE is mainly focusing on the scientific community, but would be interested in interacting with the industry stakeholders</p>
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4 Some figures and quantitative objectives: initialized/finalized projects

To have an overview of their activity with industry stakeholders, the CoEs were asked about the number of projects (both initialized and finalized) they have/had with either SMEs, Big Industry or public institutions.

It appeared that almost all CoEs (the current phase, that generally started in January 2023) had no projects done or ongoing up to July 2023, and they generally have small objectives regarding these projects (except for EXCELLERAT, Hidalgo, Cheese and BioExcel). The detailed feedbacks for the CoEs are summarized in Table 3:

Table 3: Number of projects with industry or public institutions

CoE	how many projects with SMEs did you initialize/finalize:	how many projects with Big Industry did you initialize/finalize:	how many projects with public institutions are you willing to initialize/finalize during your project runtime:
EXCELLERAT-2	SSC did in EXCELLERAT P1 some tests with the software SCALES and some SMEs like earlier adopters from the area Baden Württemberg	DLR and CEFACS through optimized codes CODA and AVBP work since EXCELLERAT Phase 1 with companies like AIRBUS, ONERA, SAFRAN	this CoE focused on engineering applications. At the moment no direct engineering applications are known in the public institutions
ChEESE2	0	0	6 live exercises
CEEC	0	0	0
HiDALGO2	0	1 with Big Industry 4 with governments	2
MaX3	0	0	0
SPACE	?	?	?
MultiXScale	None at present	the CoE is performing a sub-project (use case) with a large industry (Leonardo) partner of the CoE	no plans for the moment
Plasma-PEPSC	0	0	(July 2023) Still is early to know how much at the moment. We will look at this later in the next 6-12 months.
BioExcel-3	0 as of 2023 July for BioExcel-3. Many projects in the previous funding phases	0 as of 2023 July for BioExcel-3. Many projects in the previous funding phases	We cannot say for sure at the moment
ESiWACE-3	0	0	21

5 KPIs – with regards to industry topics

To have an overview of their planned activity and their objectives in terms of numbers, regarding their interactions with industry stakeholders, the CoEs were asked about their specific KPIs when it comes to interaction with industry.

It appeared that only EXCELLERAT, Hidalgo, Cheese and BioExcel have specific KPIs linked in some way to industry topics. The detailed feedbacks for the CoEs are summarized in Table 4 below.

Table 4: KPIs of the CoEs, regarding industry topics

CoE	KPIs (specific to industry)
EXCELLERAT-2	Number of applications improved – Goal: 2 external applications with significant improvement Number of notable interactions with prospective end users – Goal: 10 Additional public-private co-publications of EXCELLERAT P2 partners with external stakeholders – Goal:5 Number of success stories released in collaboration with end users Number of SMEs, large industry introducing product or process innovations thanks to access to HPC, HPDA, AI expertise via EXCELLERAT P2 – Goal: 5 Number of common activities between companies and centre partners, that have been initiated by the centre – Goal: 10 Number of collaborations with other actions, e.g. through the CASTIEL 2 CSA, that lead to improvements for the partners – Goal 20 collaborations. Number of engineering community subgroups that regularly interact with the centre – Goal: 4 Number of participants in trainings of EXCELLERAT P2 – 150 in average per year
CEEC	-
HiDALGO2	Involvement of stakeholders in renewable energy and energy in buildings use-cases to show solutions and propose collaborations Indirect benefits for HPC systems providers like Atos
ChEESE2	8 full-IUB members following the progress of the project not only during the face-to-face and remote meetings but also through continuous feedback and validation of the PDs and related services in an operational environments and exercises.
MaX3	NONE (no initial industry interest)
SPACE	-
MultiXScale	Not specific to industry: events, ambassadors, centers using their technology
Plasma-PEPSC	NONE (no <u>initial</u> industry interest)
BioExcel-3	Not specific to industry: but they track # of events, # trained people, # tutorials etc. Monitoring the uptake of software by industry, pharma in particular.
ESiWACE-3	Interest for collaboration with industry but it is not the primary target

6 Challenges – with regards to industry topics

To have an overview of their challenges, regarding their interactions with industry stakeholders, the CoEs were asked about their difficulties or obstacles when it comes to interaction with industry. The detailed feedbacks for the CoEs are summarized in Table 5 below.

Table 5: Challenges wrt industry interactions

CoE	Challenges
EXCELLERAT-2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Level of technology readiness from services and products: this level should be high enough that potential industry users can use them in the middle/long term without any support from researchers. • Interoperability: Integrating diverse hardware, software, and networking technologies from different vendors and research institutions can be complex. • Data sharing and privacy: Exchanging data and resources among different organizations while safeguarding sensitive information and adhering to data privacy regulations can be a challenging task. • Cultural and organizational differences: CoE Excellerat involves collaboration between multiple institutions, each with its own organizational structure, work practices, and culture. • Funding and resource allocation: Sustaining a long-term collaborative effort often requires securing funding and managing resources across different partners with varying budget constraints. • Intellectual property concerns: Collaborating on cutting-edge research and development projects can raise issues related to intellectual property rights and sharing of innovations. • Coordination resources: Effective coordination is vital to ensure that all partners are on the same page, making progress, and addressing any roadblocks promptly. • Time constraints: Working on complex and ambitious projects like exascale computing applications requires a long-term commitment.
CEEC	-
HiDALGO2	?
ChEESE2	A proper continuous interaction during 4 years is foreseen although some players may change the interlocutor during the time frame
MaX3	Potential industrial users of codes are a key target, though material simulations are not very easy to go to the market, thus it is difficult to have a real industrial uptake. Going through SW vendors may increase visibility. Actions: outreach through events, SW vendors and specific requests, industrial staff training
SPACE	-
MultiXScale	Visibility and Outreach centred both in industry and academic fields: "Elevator pitches" to ensure the engagement from the community. Training infrastructure to support training activities Training activities related to different topics (application-specific, software stack, using EESSI, contributing an application or library to the shared software stack)
Plasma-PEPSC	PLASMA only started (date 11.07.2023), and building their CoE, hence they focus first on academia (for up to the next 6 months).
BioExcel-3	Each company has rather specific needs and the CoE does not have enough resources to provide customs/in-depth support
ESiWACE-3	Industry is not the primary target; thus the project results are not targeting this audience

7 Budget, material and resources available to interact with industry

To have an overview of their budget, material and resources available to interact with industry stakeholders, the CoEs were asked about their available resources (financial or experts) when it comes to interaction with industry. The detailed feedbacks for the CoEs are summarized in

Table 6.

Table 6: Budget, material and resources available to interact with industry

CoE	Budget	Material	Resources
EXCELLERAT-2	existing budget for the material defined in the GA	Animations/videos E Flyers (sectors, success stories, use cases) Participation in a booth in major events, training, and workshops + other costs for events in partners' premises Service portal to display the offers regarding the engineering field: https://services.excellerat.eu/ Website to inform all stakeholders from the EXCELLERAT CoE community Social media channels like LinkedIn, Twitter, YouTube, and Spotify	competences in digital marketing, E-commerce management, platform management public relations (event organization, media relations, social media, E flyers, etc) are partly existing at the EXCELLERAT CoE and necessary to reach these goals
CEEC	Type 1 CoE No budget to interact with industry	Type 1 CoE No material to interact with industry	Type 1 CoE No resources to interact with industry
HiDALGO2	Possible collaborations - to be discussed with the technical experts Rather targeting governmental organisations	Portal, demos and other graphic materials	Specific WP6 about collaboration, but not really focused on industry No budget for PoC
ChEESE2	TBD according to the interactions and live exercises format	Only for dissemination purposes	-
MaX3	Type 1 CoE No budget BUT OPEN TO COLLABORATION	Type 1 CoE No material to interact with industry BUT OPEN TO COLLABORATION , and Service Portal: http://www.max-centre.eu/services	Type 1 CoE No resources to interact with industry BUT OPEN TO COLLABORATION
SPACE	Type 1 CoE No budget to interact with industry	Type 1 CoE No material to interact with industry	Type 1 CoE No resources to interact with industry
MultiXScale	No budget for PoC studies	website, training portal	Interest to interact with industry but no PoC budget
Plasma-PEPSC	No budget for PoC studies	Training could potentially be of interest for industry users	Cloud providers are providing apps software as services to their users/customers

BioExcel-3	No specific budget	Service Portal: https://bioexcel.eu/services/	Open-source software, training material and events open to industry participants
ESiWACE-3	Budget planned for services	Service Portal: https://www.esiwace.eu/services	Budget planned for services

8 Preferences or current objectives in terms of collaborations

To have an overview of their preferred collaborations (with other CoEs, with the NCCs, with CASTIEL2 or other stakeholders) with regards to topics linked to interaction with industry stakeholders, the CoEs were asked to provide their suggestions regarding potential collaborations. The detailed feedbacks for the CoEs are summarized in Table 7.

Table 7: Collaboration preferences or objectives

CoE	Suggestions of collaboration (with NCCs, wrt industry topics)
EXCELLERAT-2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Industry outreach and engagement: Actively reach out to industries and establish communication channels to understand their specific needs, challenges, and areas of interest. Regularly engage with industry stakeholders through workshops, seminars, and conferences. • Industry-driven research projects: Collaborate with industries to identify research projects that have practical applications and can benefit from CoE EXCELLERAT advancements. • Co-development initiatives: Partner with industry players in co-development efforts, where both parties contribute resources, expertise, and knowledge to jointly work on cutting-edge projects and solutions. • Data sharing and privacy mechanisms: Implement robust data sharing frameworks that ensure the confidentiality and security of industry data while allowing researchers to access relevant information for research purposes. • Technology transfer and knowledge exchange: Facilitate the transfer of technologies and best practices from CoE Excellerat to industries, helping them adopt and integrate these advancements into their workflows and processes. That will be done in detail later on through the Exploitation strategy of the KERs Owners • Collaborative training programs: Offer joint training programs and workshops that cater to the industry. • Industry-academia partnerships: Foster partnerships between CoE Excellerat and academic institutions to bring together academic research expertise and industry application knowledge. • Intellectual property management: Establish clear guidelines for managing intellectual property rights resulting from collaborative projects. Demonstrations and showcases: Organize events where CoE Excellerat can demonstrate the practical applications and benefits to industries. Showcasing successful case studies can inspire more industries to collaborate and invest in HPC research. • Industry advisory board: Form an industry advisory board comprising representatives from various sectors to provide guidance, feedback, and industry-specific insights to CoE Excellerat. This board can help align research efforts with industry needs and trends. • Long-term partnerships: Focus on building long-term, sustained partnerships with industries rather than one-off collaborations. Long-lasting relationships can lead to more substantial impact and continuous progress in HPC applications.
CEEC	-
HiDALGO2	<p>Already collaborated with a NCC in the previous project by organizing a training day for people interested in how they addressed HPDA => could be replicated for other NCCs</p> <p>Open to collaborations with NCCs attending events and looking for collaboration with industries (small demos, simple customization of some use-cases? Usage of some results from the project)</p>
ChEESSE2	<p>Possible collaborations - to be discussed with the technical experts</p> <p>Rather targeting governmental organisations, but also private companies in a 2 level Industry & Users Board. Full IUB Members are meant to have technical discussions with the Pilot(s) Leader(s) and co-design the final live exercises showing the actual impact of the ChEESSE-2 foreground and the potential adoption of it beyond the end of the CoE. Either way, IUB members will be kept informed about the progress of the project as well as from events, etc.</p>

MaX3	Open to collaborate wt NCCs and industries wt our codes and open to provide expertise for training (both in NCC-run courses and by hosting industrial researchers in our labs)
SPACE	-
MultiXScale	Collaboration with EuroCC2-Italy and EDIH-DAMAS, targeting Aerospace & Automotive sectors
Plasma-PEPSC	Collaboration with IT companies (interest probably only at a later stage)
BioExcel-3	Promote our training events, webinars, workshops, user guides and support structures to pharma companies which might be interested in adopting the tools in their drug discovery processes.
ESiWACE-3	Disseminate the services provided in ESiWACE2 and ESiWACE3 to the NCC targeting industry topics

9 Contact people for industry topics

Table 8: contact people in the CoEs for industry topics

CoE	Champion	Email	Deputy	Email			
Excellerat2	Anne-Bernard Bedouet	bedouet@siccos-bw.de	Samir Ben Chaabane	samir.ben-chaabane@teratec.eu			
BioExcel3	Javier Iglesias	javier.iglesias@nostrumbiodiscovery.com	Rossen Apostolov	rossen@kth.se	Richard Norman	richard@normanconsulting.no	
Cheese	Joan Farnos	joan.farnos@bsc.es	Tomaso Esposti Ongaro	tomaso.espostiongaro@ingv.it	Arnau Folch	afolch@geo3bcn.csic.es	
HIDALGO	Zoltán Horváth	horvathz@math.sze.hu	Jesus Gorroñogoitia Cruz	jesus.gorronogoitia@eviden.com	László Környei	laszlo.kornyei@math.sze.hu	
MultiXScale	Alan O'Cais	alan.ocais@cecam.org	Neja Samec	neja.samec@cmm.ki.si	Antonio Sciarappa	antonio.sciarappa@leonardo.com	Carlo Cavazzoni
Max3	Luisa Neri	luisa.neri@max-centre.eu	Nicola Spallanzani	nicola.spallanzani@max-centre.eu			
Esiwace3	Xavier Yepes	xavier.yepes@bsc.es	Erwan Raffin (Eviden-ATOS)	erwan.raffin@atos.net			
PlasmaPEPS C	Stefano Markidis	markidis@kth.se	Jeremy J. Williams	jjwil@kth.se			
SPACE	no industry collaboration						
CEEC	Niclas Jansson	njansson@kth.se					

10 Conclusions

This information collected by WP4 of CASTIEL is valid at the date of August 21st, 2023. The information collected up to July 2023 and presented in this document will be updated regularly (at least yearly) thanks to the regular discussions (quarterly telcos planned with CASTIEL-WP4) that will take place with the CoEs.

Thanks to this gathering of information, CASTIEL-WP4 will target the key needs or challenges of the CoEs and foster the preferred or relevant collaborations among the CoEs that have common industry interests or objectives. This information, that will be shared with EuroCC2 will also allow the NCCs to better frame what the CoEs are, particularly what the CoEs are aiming at when it comes to industry and what they could do together or what they did not achieve yet.